

ISSN 2181-2357

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

VOLUME 2,
Issue 9
2022

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ.

A. M. Abdullayev

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

2021 yil noyabrdan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi. 16+

2-tom, 9 -son.

Sentyabr 2022 y.

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, Rector of FerPI

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, A.A.Shermukhamedovsh, Y.S.A. H.A.Akramov, M.X.Hakimov, Sh.M.Iskandarova, Z.M.Sobirova, A.M.Muxtorova, L.M.Babaxo'jaeva.

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IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti administratsiyasi huzuridagi axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligida ro'yxatga olingan.

Ro'yxatga olish № 1189 Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

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Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.

Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2022. T. 2. №9. <https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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2022 Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

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«Al-Ferganus» LLC.
A. M. Abdullaev
“International journal of theoretical and practical research”
Scientific Journal.
Published since November 2021.
Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 2, Issue 6-8

September, 2022.

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Phone +998971003888

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E-mail:

alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**

<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2022: 5,962

<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
Registration No. 1189 dated 17-06-2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2022). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 2(9).

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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«Al-Ferganus» ООО.

А. М. Абдуллаев

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Издается с ноября 2021 г.

Выходит один раз в месяц. 16+

Том 2, Номер 9.

Сентябрь 2022 г.

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

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Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) 8.7 / 2021

[http://journalseeker.research](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[bib.com/view/issn/2181-](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[2357](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

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[ort.php?id=21994](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации

Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 1189 от 17-06-2021.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

Тип лицензии CC поддерживаемый журналом: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2022. Т. 2. №9.

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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2022, Фергана, Узбекистан

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QR CODE of this issue of the magazine

**International journal of
theoretical and practical
research****Scientific Journal****Year: 2022 Issue: 9****Volume: 2****Published:****30.09.2022**<http://alferganus.uz>

QR-Article

Citation:

Abdullaev, A.M., (2022). Trends in Uzbekistan's socioeconomic development during its years of independence. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 7-19.

Abdullaev, A.M. (2022). Trends in Uzbekistan's socioeconomic development during its years of independence. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 7-19.

Doi:<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7185924>**Abdullaev, Alisher Makhmudovich**

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UDC 65.9(5Y); 172.12: 008

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7185924

**TRENDS IN UZBEKISTAN'S SOCIOECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT DURING
ITS YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE**

Abstract: *This article examines the stages of economic development in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's continued socioeconomic growth is detailed, and the expansion of small company and private enterprise is evaluated. The current stages of economic development are presented. Uzbekistan's independence turned 31 years old. During these years, Uzbekistan itself has seen significant transformation, while the world surrounding it has undergone fundamental technological, economic, political, and geo-economic shifts. But one thing has remained the same: the commitment to reforms aimed at enhancing the economy's competitiveness and residents' living conditions.*

Keywords: *Economy, small company, development, national interests, international collaboration, extra-economic linkages, and liberalization of the economy are the key terms.*

**ТЕНДЕНЦИИ СОЦИАЛЬНО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ
УЗБЕКИСТАНА ЗА ГОДЫ НЕЗАВИСИМОСТИ****Абдуллаев, Алишер Махмудович***к.э.н., доцент,*

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются этапы экономического развития Республики Узбекистан. Подробно описан продолжающийся социально-экономический рост Узбекистана, а также дана оценка расширению малых компаний и частного предпринимательства. Представлены текущие этапы экономического развития. Независимости Узбекистана исполнилось 31 год. За эти годы сам Узбекистан претерпел значительные преобразования, в то время как окружающий его мир претерпел фундаментальные технологические, экономические, политические и геоэкономические сдвиги. Но одно осталось неизменным: приверженность реформам, направленным на повышение конкурентоспособности экономики и условий жизни жителей.

Ключевые слова: Экономика, малая компания, развитие, национальные интересы, международное сотрудничество, внеэкономические связи и либерализация экономики являются ключевыми терминами.

МУСТАҚИЛЛИК ЙИЛЛАРИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ТЕНДЕНЦИЯЛАРИ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада Ўзбекистон Республикасида иқтисодий ривожланиш босқичлари кўриб чиқилган. Ўзбекистонда давом этаётган ижтимоий-иқтисодий ўсиш батафсил муҳокама қилиниб, кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик соҳасининг кенгайиши баҳоланади. Иқтисодий ривожланишнинг ҳозирги босқичлари келтирилган. Мамлакатимиз мустақилликка эришганига 31 йил тўлди. Бу йиллар давомида Ўзбекистоннинг ўзи муҳим ўзгаришларни, унинг атрофидаги дунё эса фундаментал технологик, иқтисодий, сиёсий ва геоиқтисодий ўзгаришларни бошдан кечирди. Аммо иқтисодиётнинг рақобатбардошлиги ва аҳолининг яшаш шароитларини оширишга қаратилган ислохотлар ўз ахамиятини йўқотмади.

Калит сўзлар: Иқтисодиёт, кичик компания, ривожланиш, миллий манфаатлар, халқаро ҳамкорлик, иқтисодий алоқалар ва иқтисодиётни эркинлаштириш асосий шартлардир.

Introduction

Today, few individuals recall the circumstances surrounding the establishment of an independent Uzbekistan. In the latter years of the Soviet Union, trains and ships collided and the government crumbled, and the country's order fell apart. Bloody battles happened in many former Soviet countries, but only in Uzbekistan were these conflicts

averted. It was perhaps the first time in the post-Soviet realm that it was possible to avoid the Osh scenario from playing out in a potentially volatile area - the Uzbek portion of the Fergana Valley.

The economic situation and standard of living were far from satisfactory. In 1990, the per capita output of national revenue in Uzbekistan was twice as low as the average level of the Union, and labour productivity in industry was 40% lower than the average level of the Union, while in agricultural it was twice as low. Per capita production of consumer products in the republic was 40% of the Union average. Nearly 45% of the population had an average total per capita income of less than 75 rubles per month, compared to less than 12% for the entire country.

With the fall of the Soviet Union, economic links began to deteriorate, production decreased, and living standards and social protection fell precipitously. Due to its geographical location, Uzbekistan faced the most challenging transport isolation conditions. In the shortest time possible, it was essential to establish national statehood, defense, diplomacy, a currency (which was established on 1 July 1994), energy and food safety, and to penetrate world markets, seas, and oceans with its goods.

In these difficult circumstances, it developed its own model of transition to market relations, taking into account the specific conditions and characteristics of the republic, its traditions, customs, and way of life. This model was based on the following five principles: the economy has priority over politics, the state is the main reformer, the rule of law, and strong social protection are implemented in stages. These ideas continue to underpin the ongoing reforms, which have enabled the country to avoid a number of economic and political shocks experienced by other post-Soviet nations.

In general, the reform approach chosen during the initial phase of independence has met expectations. In retrospect, according to a UNDP assessment from the mid-1990s, Uzbekistan was the first post-Soviet nation to stop its output drop and move toward economic growth. Uzbekistan had the smallest fall in output among the post-Soviet states. In the most challenging economic conditions, the level of social protection was greater than in other post-Soviet nations. While other post-Soviet nations were losing entire industries, Uzbekistan was building new ones from scratch, with the automobile industry serving as a notable example.

Prior to gaining independence, Uzbekistan had never produced its own automobiles. In 1994, the UzDaewooAuto joint venture was founded between the Daewoo Corporation of South Korea and Uzbekistan. Due to Daewoo's bankruptcy in 2008, the company was changed into a joint venture with American automaker General Motors. Today, this existing Uzbek company, UzAuto Motors, which is independent of external partners, continues to manufacture and export automobiles of various brands.

Main portion

New changes

One cannot deny, however, that by the middle of the decade, the development of the Uzbek economy began to stall due to excessive administrative regulation and closedness, which prevented the full utilization of market incentives for its development. Consequently, the newly elected President of Uzbekistan in 2016, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, initiated a new period of comprehensive changes in all aspects of life. In February of

2017, he approved the Action Strategy for Uzbekistan's five development priorities for 2017-2021. Improving state and social construction, ensuring the rule of law and reforming the judicial and legal system, developing and liberalizing the economy, developing the social sphere, ensuring security, and implementing a balanced and constructive foreign policy are among the most important aspects of the new phase. In the past few years, significant progress has been made in each of these fields. Observe a few of them.

Despite the adoption of the Concept of e-government development in Uzbekistan in 2004 for the purpose of enhancing public administration, considerable progress has not been made in this area until lately. Nonetheless, in December 2016, the President issued an order for the opening of virtual and people's reception halls in each district and city. And today, state electronic services in Uzbekistan are provided through the following: a single portal of interactive public services (EPISP), public service centers at the President's reception offices, public reception offices of the President of Uzbekistan, virtual reception offices of the President of Uzbekistan, a portal for discussion of draft regulations, official websites, and information portals of state bodies.

In the realm of economic reforms, the currency reform generated the most reverberation around the globe. The Presidential Decree "On Foreign Exchange Policy Liberalization" was published in September 2017, allowing legal businesses and individuals to freely convert foreign currency. Prior to that time, there were three separate exchange rates: the black-market rate, the exchange rate, and the Central Bank rate. As a result, currency exchange transactions were a major issue. Another important economic reform in 2018 was the tax reform, which drew particular attention due to the widespread discussion of the Tax Policy Improvement Concept. With the release of a new edition of the Tax Code in 2020, the primary phase of the tax reform was finished. During the course of the reform, taxes on labor were cut, the gap between the general and simplified tax regimes was erased, the system of tax administration was enhanced, and additional improvements were implemented.

During the course of the reforms, various administrative and bureaucratic obstacles to entrepreneurial activity were removed, a business-friendly climate was created, the necessary legal guarantees for business were supplied, and the state provided active support to entrepreneurs. In worldwide rankings, these changes were reflected. The total amount of foreign direct investment has increased despite ongoing policy adjustments (FDI),

Attractiveness of Uzbekistan rose from \$1.6 billion in 2018 to \$4.2 billion in 2019. Uzbekistan scored among the top twenty "global improvers" in the World Bank's Doing Business in 2020 report, thanks to a significant improvement in its standing over the past five years. At the same time, weak government progress in reducing the dominance of state monopolies in the economy, a lack of transparency in government procurement, growing concerns about protecting private property, and inadequate legislation to protect intellectual property rights have a negative impact on the investment climate in Uzbekistan. The tight legal and regulatory structure with its numerous bylaws, as well as the lack of competition and market access, prevents investors from pursuing potentially

lucrative business possibilities in Uzbekistan. The spread of COVID-19 has altered investment patterns and rendered FDI a globally competitive commodity.

Dietary safety

Providing food independence and food security is one of the most significant accomplishments in the history of independent Uzbekistan, which has taken on added significance in light of the pandemic's food-related issues.

On the eve of independence, the country imported an average of 3 million tons of grain, whereas only 2.038 million tons were harvested in Uzbekistan in 1990, resulting in a severe food scarcity. In 1989, for instance, 89.3% of respondents said they consumed insufficient quantities of meat items, 56.5% of dairy goods, 55.3% of sugar, 49.55% of sweets, and 17.5% of potatoes. In light of the necessity to ensure food independence, it was agreed in 1989 to allot more than 400 thousand hectares of irrigated land to homestead lands, whose area was later increased to 700 thousand hectares and used for food production. Since 1995, the area devoted to cotton has decreased drastically from more than 50 to 36.1%, and the area devoted to grain crops has climbed from 24 to 44-45% of the total area devoted to crops, providing food independence.

During the current era of economic development, a special focus has been placed on bolstering food security.

In January 2018, the Presidential Decree "On steps to further assure food security of the country" was published, establishing a series of measures to address challenges to the stability of the food market and to secure the supply of food. Food security is also a goal of the ongoing structural changes in agriculture. A shift to a cluster system of agricultural production with a high degree of processing in clusters of agricultural raw materials, the abolition of the state order system for cotton, and a reduction in the state order for cereals have been implemented as part of an agricultural reform. Cotton planting is decreasing, and as a result, 170.5 thousand hectares of irrigated land are being developed for the cultivation of cereals, vegetables, oil crops, orchards, and vineyards, and food production is increasing. In 2021, the index's ninth edition was published. The GFSI examines food availability, availability, quality, and safety in addition to natural resources and sustainability in 113 nations.

Uzbekistan's overall score declined by 0.7 points from 2019 and 2021, placing it at position 78 out of 113. During the epidemic, the success of food security in other nations had a significant reversal, which explains the improvement in ranking. The score allowed Uzbekistan to maintain its position within the group of nations with moderate food security. Economic structure alterations

During the period from 2017 to 2021, the government of Uzbekistan conducted a number of economic changes, including currency exchange rate reforms and international trade control, and liberalised prices for a variety of products and services. The government is now focused on eliminating structural obstacles to GDP development. For instance, underdeveloped factor markets and the predominance of state-owned businesses and banks in the economy.

The subsequent phase of socioeconomic reforms will result in a private sector that is larger and more competitive. This is required in order to dismantle an inefficient system

characterized by considerable state involvement in numerous economic sectors and the creation of few jobs.

Approximately 7.5% of Uzbek nationals lived below the World Bank's poverty level for lower-middle income countries in 2021. Many of them reside near to this line and have a high chance of dropping below it. One out of every six homes in the country has a member working abroad, primarily in Russia.

Initiated during the COVID-19 pandemic, reforms to enhance the provision of social assistance to residents will assist in expanding social protection coverage and labor market support programmes for citizens. These steps will aid in preventing a rapid increase in poverty throughout the nation. It is anticipated that Russia's invasion of Ukraine will reduce Uzbekistan's GDP growth to 3.6% in 2022. This is a result of the halving of migrant workers' remittances and their return to their home countries, record-high global oil and food prices, and disruptions in international trade logistics chains, investment inflows, and financial systems.

To prevent a rise in poverty among the populace, additional social protection and labor market assistance initiatives will be required. A tighter government monetary policy, higher earnings from commodity exports, and reduced spending on public investment in the economy will create budgetary space to fulfill present requirements and preserve macroeconomic stability.

In 2021, the Uzbek economy increased by 7.4%. Strong growth in the industrial and service sectors helped to ameliorate the still-weak growth in agriculture. Migrant workers' remittances increased again. However, it only partially offset the huge decline in gold revenue (down 29%). This resulted in an increase in the current account deficit from 5% of GDP in 2020 to 6.6% of GDP in 2021.

The deficit expanded from 4.5 percent of GDP in 2020 to 6.2 percent of GDP in 2021. Almost all of the funding came from external sources. However, they did not exceed the \$5.5 billion annual cap established by the government. Inflation continued to drop, averaging 10.8% in 2021 (compared to 12.9% in 2020). Inflation continues to be driven by higher domestic and international food and transportation expenses.

Reductions in government-subsidized lending and high real interest rates have slowed the growth of loans from 31% in 2020 to 18% in 2021. The banking system continues to function without interruption. The capital and liquidity buffers remain in excess of the statutory minimums. In order to limit dollarization of the banking sector, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan has increased the minimum reserve requirement on foreign currency deposits from 14% to 18% in 2021.

In 2021, the unemployment rate will be 9.6%, down from 10.5% in 2020. However, it has not yet returned to the 9 percent rate seen in the United States prior to the COVID-19 epidemic.

Prospects for economic growth

The war in Ukraine will reduce Uzbekistan's GDP growth to 3.6% in 2022, compared to pre-crisis projections of approximately 6%. The predicted 50% decline in migrant workers' remittances as a result of the lower ruble and the collapse of the Russian economy, as well as higher oil, wheat, and vegetable oil costs, will have a significant negative impact on private consumption growth. Given the considerable dependence of

the national economy on Russian capital imports and bank financing of public and private investment projects, it is anticipated that investment inflows will also decelerate.

Even though Uzbekistan will profit from strong global commodity prices (gold, copper, and natural gas), it is anticipated that a decline in remittances of up to 6 percent of GDP will expand the current account deficit to 10 percent of GDP in 2022. In addition, foreign direct investment inflows will be restricted in general in 2022. The recovery will require time.

In turn, the increased current account deficit will be covered by fresh external borrowings from the government and the utilization of international reserves.

In 2022, it is anticipated that the government deficit will decline to 4% of GDP. The anticipated fiscal consolidation in 2023 will likely be delayed. The public debt is expected to peak at 42 percent of GDP in 2022-23. By the end of 2024, it should level off at approximately 40% of GDP.

Surpassing transportation isolation

The inherited nature of Central Asian borders did not ensure transport security for a sovereign state, as products had to be transported via neighboring nations. This issue was resolved by the construction of new railways and roads across mountain passes leading to the Fergana Valley and the Surkhandarya region. Uzbekistan is now self-sufficient in terms of transport; thus it is no longer necessary to cross international borders for internal shipments, which was previously exceedingly inconvenient for the nation and its people.

Throughout its years of independence, the country has established a well-developed network of trains and motorways, as well as international airports to accommodate its international and transit traffic requirements. And the country's internal highways are becoming more comfortable to travel on, with high-speed trains connecting the nation's main cities into a unified network.

Tashkent's roadways and new traffic interchanges, as well as the city's general appearance, bear little resemblance to what they were prior to Uzbekistan's independence. Practically, it is a new city that accommodates international events with success.

Moreover, the separation of Uzbekistan from the oceans by at least the borders of two states substantially raises the cost of transportation, consequently increasing the price of imported and exported goods. As a result, the policy of establishing the most efficient transport routes for cargo transportation was given special consideration, and there have been significant shifts in the movement of commodities since independence.

The Soviet Union exported Uzbek cotton to Russia, Uzbek gas to the "center" (the gas pipeline was named "Central Asia-Center"), and from there, to a lesser extent, to Europe. From Russia, Belarus, and Ukraine, machinery and equipment were being shipped to Uzbekistan. In the 1990s, it was necessary to maintain the functionality of transport corridors to external markets via the Baltic States and the Far East, as well as to open new corridors for Uzbek goods, because the capacity of markets along inherited corridors was rapidly declining due to the general decline in the economy and standard of living in the post-Soviet region. Uzbekistan's economy also required new, modern equipment, which the CIS industry could no longer provide, nor could it afford to pay the global price for Uzbek cotton.

In this context, new transport corridors in the direction of Europe through Iran (the Mashhad-Seraskh-Tejen highway, which connected the Central Asian and Iranian railways) and Transcaucasia (the TRACECA trans-Caucasus railroad) were quickly put into operation in 1996, allowing Uzbek cotton and other goods to be transported to Europe. In particular, I recall the anecdote of one of the respondents to Economic Review magazine who accompanied the initial shipment of Uzbek cotton through the TRACECA route. He described how difficult and morally challenging it was to drive through Georgia, where the war had just ended and the smoldering wreckage along the way were still visible.

Nevertheless, time did not stand still, and the global economy was undergoing a huge transformation. The European industrial sector was relocating to Asia and no longer required major quantities of cotton and other raw materials. Asia, led by China, was undergoing fast economic growth, necessitating an increasing demand for raw commodities. The establishment of a full-fledged transport corridor to Persian Gulf ports via Iran paved the door for Uzbek commodities to reach South and South-East Asia, with the majority of Uzbek cotton bound for this region.

As a result of the global financial crisis, gas prices in Europe as a whole fell from their prior record highs. This posed a difficulty for Russia's gas imports from Central Asia, as it was already supplying Europe with sufficient quantities of its own gas. And natural gas flow is reversed. Turkmen and subsequently Uzbek gas were the first to reach China.

The distribution of machinery and equipment shipments to Uzbekistan has also shifted geographically. In the nineties-zero, Western sophisticated equipment eliminated supplies of poorly competitive CIS products. However, the situation has changed. First, the equipment and machinery manufactured in the West are extremely expensive, and second, they require costly maintenance, which limits the profitability of their usage in the home industry. As was the case, for example, with the American cotton harvesting "Cases," which were swiftly rendered obsolete. Numerous types of machinery (cars, buses) are now produced locally in Uzbekistan, and the importation of machinery and equipment is primarily driven by the need to master and implement new technologies.

Uzbekistan currently has reliable transport channels in all directions, including to the Baltic and Russian Far East ports, Chinese ports in the Pacific basin and Iranian ports in the Indian Ocean, as well as transit access to the European market. Nevertheless, efforts to optimize transportation corridors continue. On the agenda are the implementation of projects for the shortest railway to China via Kyrgyzstan, as well as the building of transport communications via Afghanistan to Pakistan and India, which are currently being vigorously pursued.

Social policy

In the initial era of Uzbekistan's transition to a market economy, social protection for the entire population was implemented on the basis of the necessity for substantial social protection; subsidies and benefits were applied equally to the entire population. However, this was accompanied by the reality that wealthy families also received subsidies and benefits. As a result, an emphasis was placed on targeted social support of the population, in which assistance was provided to families in genuine need. At the time,

the most significant societal impact was the 1993 law on the privatisation of state housing, which allowed residents to obtain full ownership rights to their house and thereafter dispose of it as they saw appropriate.

Since the commencement of the current phase of reforms, the strengthening of social security for the populace has received special emphasis. For the first time, the presence of poverty in the country was acknowledged by the head of state, and systematic and comprehensive efforts to eradicate it and increase social protections for the populace were initiated. In order to achieve this objective, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction and the Ministry for the Support of the Mahalla and the Family were established. The transition from previously poorly focused and effective institutions for material help distribution to systemic solutions based on digital technology has begun. Through door-to-door household visits, the actual problems and living conditions of particular families were identified.

On the basis of door-to-door visits, a registry of poor families, taking into account their issues, and the so-called "Iron Notebook" are compiled, which provided the basis for a tailored program of poverty reduction and social support. On the basis of these data, the "Single Register of Social Assistance" Information System, which offers a transparent, real-time evaluation of the degree of need of families and the eligibility of applicants, was implemented last year. Consequently, the social support system became entirely visible. In addition, as of January 1, 2021, the list of documentation required to get state social services and aid was significantly reduced.

Implementing targeted programs for the building of cheap housing and the development and modernization of road transport, engineering, and social infrastructure in order to enhance living conditions is an additional significant aspect of social support. In order to improve living conditions and amenities in rural areas, the Obod Qishloq and Obod Mahalla programs are implemented. Those in need of improved home conditions receive mortgage loans with favorable terms. In both urban and rural locations, affordable housing is being created. The provision of clean drinking water in rural areas is given considerable consideration.

Conclusion

It is impossible to discuss social policy without mentioning health care, education, and science, which are essential to human development and the improvement of human capital. If in the early years of independence, the national systems of health care and education were established, in recent years the emphasis has been on their radical reform, which aims to increase the quality of education and health care to world standards.

The globalization of the labor market, which has made it imperative for Uzbekistan to join the global educational space, which entails bringing the quality of education up to modern world standards, has been one of the primary reasons for revamping the education system in Uzbekistan since 2017. As a result of improvements in this field, Uzbekistan's system of continuous education today encompasses prekindergarten, general secondary, specialized secondary and vocational, higher and postgraduate education, as well as out-of-school education and the system of professional development and retraining.

The establishment of Presidential schools and children's music and art schools across the nation for exceptionally brilliant children is already underway. In institutes of

higher education, international teaching and grading standards are being implemented. Educational procedures already make considerable use of digital technology, which was aggressively supported by pandemic-related quarantine limitations when schools and universities taught online.

Innovative endeavors are stimulated aggressively. Higher education institutions and research institutes are in the process of establishing specialized laboratories, high technology centers, and technoparks, which facilitate the implementation of scientific and inventive advances. Numerous technoparks for the development of digital technologies have been established and are currently operational, with the intention of playing a significant role in the digitalization of the economy and other fields of endeavor.

First, primary care, emergency care, and urgent medical care are being modified within the healthcare industry. Active work is being performed on the digitalization of medical services and the implementation of a single electronic medical record, which will make it possible to store online a comprehensive history of a patient's sickness and treatment. A great deal of emphasis is also placed on preventative measures to reduce the incidence of disease, including the promotion of a healthy lifestyle and the reduction of infant and child mortality. The health sector has played a vital role in battling the coronavirus epidemic, making Uzbekistan more effective than the majority of nations.

The worldwide rankings have also reflected Uzbekistan's strong social policies in recent years. Thus, in the Human Development Index-2022, compiled annually by the UNDP, Uzbekistan ranked 89th out of 154 countries with a score of 0.017 and improved its ranking by 5 positions, which, according to the index methodology, allowed it to move into the category of countries with a medium quintile of industrial development.

According to the index report, there were positive improvements in six out of eight indicators as a result of the ongoing reforms and industrial development in our country, while two indicators experienced a fall. Uzbekistan's foreign trade turnover climbed by 16% in 2021, hitting \$42.1 billion, compared to the previous year. The number of exports climbed by 10% to \$16.6 billion, while imports increased by 20.4% to \$25.46 billion from the previous year. The export structure was dominated by manufactured products, particularly copper and steel, which surpassed gold.

Taking into account the existing sectoral structure of exports (predominance of gold, natural gas, minerals, and horticultural products), as well as the correspondingly established relations with the principal buyers of export products, the future development of the export-oriented economy of the country should be based on the expansion of the exports' nomenclature and geography. China is the largest purchaser of Uzbek commodities in East Asia. China is interested in raw materials and food products, but not those with a high degree of processing and a high added value (except for agricultural products). Certainly, it is possible to diversify exports and grow sales on the markets of the European Union and Asia-Pacific region, but the dynamics of the Uzbek economy over the past few years indicate that these markets play a subordinate role. In other words, the export expansion plan should be focused on identifying possible areas of the market for high-value-added commodities in the Commonwealth of Independent States, Eastern Europe, and neighboring countries that could be occupied by Uzbek goods.

In conclusion, it is important to note that 30 is the age at which a person reaches adulthood. In relation to the nation, this age is more akin to that of youth. During this period, however, the generation that laid the foundation for the country's freedom and endured its most terrible moments in history is departing. Simultaneously, a new generation born and raised in independent Uzbekistan is actively entering adulthood. And fewer and fewer individuals recall what life was like prior to independence and how tough it was to construct a new state. All of this must be recognized, if not remembered, for these were the years in which the basis of independence was laid. And this understanding will aid in appreciating the present more and avoiding future errors that, let's not be deceived, occurred throughout specific stages of our nation's independence.

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International journal of
theoretical and practical
research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2022 Issue: 9

Volume: 2

Published:

30.09.2022

<http://alferganus.uz>

QR-Article

Citation:

Akhunova, M.Kh., (2022). Key issues of textile industry development on the basis of implementation of innovative development strategy. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 20-26.

Axunova, M.X. (2022). Innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyasini joriy etish asosida to'qimachilik sanoatini rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 20-26.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7186100>

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UDC 334.021

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7186100

KEY ISSUES OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT ON THE BASIS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

Abstract: *Presidential and government decisions aimed at rapid development of the textile and sewing-knitting industry in our country have been adopted, state programs are being developed. State programs aimed at modernization and diversification of the textile industry are expansion of the volume and types of ready-made competitive products that are in high demand in foreign markets.*

Key words: *textile industry, raw cotton, finished product with added value, fabrics.*

INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYASINI JORIY ETISH ASOSIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: *Mamlakatimizda to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatini jadal rivojlantirishga qaratilgan Prezident va hukumat qarorlari qabul qilindi, davlat dasturlari ishlab chiqilmoqda. To‘qimachilik sanoatini modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilishga qaratilgan davlat dasturlari tashqi bozorlarda talab yuqori bo‘lgan ishlab chiqarilayotgan tayyor raqobatbardosh mahsulotlarning hajmi va turlarini kengaytirish hisoblanadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *to‘qimachilik sanoati, paxta xom ashyosi, qo‘shimcha qiymatga ega tayyor mahsulot, matolar.*

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ТЕКСТИЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ НА ОСНОВЕ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ СТРАТЕГИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ

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Аннотация: *В нашей стране принимаются решения Президента и правительства, направленные на опережающее развитие текстильной и швейной промышленности, разрабатываются государственные программы. Государственные программы, направленные на модернизацию и диверсификацию текстильной промышленности, заключаются в расширении объемов и видов готовой конкурентоспособной продукции, пользующейся повышенным спросом на внешних рынках.*

Ключевые слова: *текстильная промышленность, хлопковое сырье, готовая продукция с добавленной стоимостью, ткани.*

Кирish

O‘zbekiston to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoati iqtisodiyotining real sektorida yuqori ulushga ega bo‘lgan va ishlab chiqarish zanjirini to‘liq qamrab olgan yagona sanoat sohasi hisoblanadi. To‘qimachilik sanoati O‘zbekiston sanoatining eng rivojlangan va yuqori rentabelli tarmoqlaridan hisoblanadi [1-12].

So‘nggi yillarda Respublikamizda to‘qimachilik, tikuv-trikotaj, charm-poyabzal va mo‘ynachilik tarmoqlarini rivojlantirish, ishlab chiqarilayotgan tayyor mahsulotlarning turlari va assortimentini kengaytirish, shuningdek, tarmoq korxonalarining investitsiya va eksport faoliyatini har tomonlama qo‘llab-quvvatlash bo‘yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Sohaga qaratilayotgan alohida e‘tibor tufayli O‘zbekiston nafaqat paxta xomashyosi yetishtiruvchi, balki uni qayta ishlash salohiyati yuksalib borayotgan

davlatlar qatoridan joy oldi. Har doim yengil sanoat aholi bandligining yuqori darajasini ta'minlovchi yetakchi tarmoq bo'lib kelgan [8-14].

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlar tahlili

Sanoatni rivojlantirishning dolzarbligi va iqtisodiyotni takomillashtirishda tutgan o'rningining nihoyat darajada kengligi bilan doimiy ravishda tadqiqotchi olimlarning diqqat markazida bo'lgan. Xususan, mavzu yuzasidan xorijlik olimlardan Yu.Rodionov, R.S.Porter, D. Deveryuks, B.Roberts, R.N. Nureevlar ilmiy yangiliklar yaratgan bo'lsalar, mahalliy olimlardan Yo.A.Abdullaev, A.Abduhamidov, U.Muxitdinov, A.A.Ortikov, X.Ishbutaeva, SH.Nizomova, E.X.Maxmudov, M.Isoqovlar bir qator ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borishga muvaffaq bo'lishgan. Xususan, A.Artikov "O'zbekistonda sanoatni rivojlantirishning qator imkoniyatlari, geografik va iqtisodiy omillari"ga, M.P.Narziqulov "Sanoatni rivojlanish strategiyasini ishlab chiqish jarayonida asosiy e'tibor tarkibiy o'zgarishlarga qaratilganligi"ga, E.X.Maxmudov "Sanoat tarmoqlari rivojlanishiga sharoit yaratishning strategik yo'nalishlari birinchi navbatda byudjet, soliq, pul kredit, narx va valyuta siyosati kabi vositalarni qamrab olgan qulay makroiqtisodiy muhitni yaratish"ga, bog'liqliklariga alohida to'xtalib o'tishgan.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

To'qimachilik sanoatining O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotida tutgan rolining yuqoriligi, tarmoqning rivoji uchun zarur bo'lgan mahalliy xomashyoning mavjudligi va malakali ishchi kuchining yetarliligidir. Endigi maqsad esa, ushbu imkoniyatlardan to'liq va samarali foydalangan holda ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini samaradorligini oshirishdan iborat. Jahon bozorlaridagi raqobatning kuchayishi, texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi, o'z navbatida sohaga oid ilmiy izlanishlar olib borishni taqozo etadi [17-19].

Tahlil va natijalar

Respublika to'qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida yuqori va barqaror o'sish sur'atlarini ta'minlash, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va o'zlashtirish, raqobatbardosh mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish va eksport qilish, modernizatsiya qilishning strategik muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan loyihalarini amalga oshirish hisobiga yuqori texnologiyali yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish, korxonalarni texnik va texnologik yangilash, ilg'or "klaster modeli"ni joriy etishga qaratilgan tarkibiy qayta tashkil etishni yanada chuqurlashtirish bo'yicha tizimli ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda [12-19]. Jumladan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining «To'qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatini qo'llab-quvvatlashga doir kechiktirib bo'lmaydigan chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida» gi 2020 yil 5 maydagi PF-5989-son Farmoni va «Yengil sanoatni yanada rivojlantirish va tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni rag'batlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida» gi 2019 yil 16 sentyabrdagi PQ-4453-son qarori mamlakatimizda mazkur sohani yanada rivojlantirishni ta'minlashga qaratilgan amaliy chora-tadbirlar izchil ro'yobga chiqarilayotganligi isbotidir. Shu bilan birga, to'qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoati rivojlanishining har tomonlama tahlili, raqobatning kuchayishi sharoitida jahon bozorining o'zgaruvchan kon'yunkturasi sohani davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash, shuningdek, yanada barqaror va jadal rivojlanishi mexanizmlarini ishlab chiqish hamda

amalga oshirishni taqozo etmoqda. Trikotajdan tayyorlangan kiyimlar salmogʻi muntazam ortib bormoqda. Bu trikotaj buyumlarining xizmat vazifasining yuqoriligi va iqtisodiy tejamligi bilan bogʻliq [20-24]. 2022- yilning dastlabki ikki oyida Oʻzbekiston 15 ta xorijiy davlatlarga qiymati 45,6 mln AQSH dollariga teng boʻlgan qariyb 8 ming tonna trikotaj mahsulotlarini eksport qilgan. Trikotaj mahsulotlari eksporti hajmi oʻtgan yilning mos davri bilan solishtirilganda 8,4 mln AQSH dollariga oshgan. Shu davr ichida Oʻzbekiston trikotaj mahsulotlarini eng koʻp eksport qilgan davlatlar: Rossiya – 14,5 mln, Qirgʻiziston – 14,2 mln, Italiya – 8,6 mln, Ukraina – 2,8 mln AQSH dollariga teng [26].

2022- yilning ikki oyida trikotaj mahsulotlarini eng koʻp eksport qilgan hududlar:

Toshkent shahri – 19,1 mln, Toshkent viloyati – 9,1 mln, Andijon viloyati – 6,4 mln, Buxoro viloyati – 3 mln AQSH dollarini tashkil qildi.

Toʻqimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish, sohani jadal rivojlantirish va diversifikatsiya qilish uchun qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratish, toʻqimachilikda yarimtayyor mahsulotlarni chuqur qayta ishlashga investitsiyalar hajmini va tayyor mahsulotlar eksportini oshirishdagi sayyi harakatlar natijasida:

- 2019-2025-yillarda toʻqimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatini jadal rivojlantirish Konsepsiyasi tasdiqlandi

-ishlab chiqariladigan tayyor mahsulotning kamida 80 foizini eksport qiladigan tikuv-trikotaj korxonalariga tijorat banklarining kreditlari boʻyicha foizlarni toʻlash bilan bogʻliq xarajatlar Oʻzbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishni qoʻllab-quvvatlash davlat jamgʻarmasi mablagʻlari hisobidan qoplanadi

- birja savdolari orqali paxta tolasini sotishda qatʻiy talab qilinadigan bank kafolatlari bekor qilindi

-qoʻshilgan qiymat soligʻi jahon bozorlarida shakllangan narxlardan qatʻi nazar, paxta tolasining amaldagi sotish narxidan kelib chiqqan holda hisoblanadi

-respublikada ishlab chiqariladigan paxta ip-kalavalarning butun hajmini qayta ishlash hisobiga 2025-yilga borib toʻqimachilik mahsulotlari eksporti hajmini 7 milliard AQSH dollariga yetkazish

- “Oʻzstandart” agentligi “Oʻztoʻqimachilik sanoat” uyushmasi bilan birgalikda toʻqimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoati mahsulotlariga ularni sinovdan oʻtkazish usullariga talablarni belgilovchi standartlar boʻyicha amaldagi normativ-huquqiy hujjatlarni xatlovdan oʻtkazsin va xalqaro meʼyorlarni hisobga olgan holda qayta koʻrib chiqilishi lozim boʻlgan standartlar belgilandi.

Xulosa va takliflar

Yuqoridagi yuksak maqsadlarga erishish uchun quyidagi yoʻnalishlarga alohida oʻrgʻu berishni taklif etamiz :

-to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoati uchun samarali raqobatbardosh muhitni shakllantirish;

- ichki va tashqi bozorlarda to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoati mahsulotlarining raqobatbardoshligini ta‘minlash maqsadida printsipial jihatdan yangi mahsulot va texnologiya turlarini o‘zlashtirish;

- ishlab chiqarishni mahalliyashtirish;

- to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoati mahsulotlarining eksport salohiyatini kengaytirish

Xulosa o‘rnida aytish joizki, to‘qimachilik va tikuv-trikotaj sanoatini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirilib, to‘qimachilik sanoati sohasida malakali kadrlarga bo‘lgan ehtiyoj ta‘minlansa, mamlakatimizda keng turdagi sifatli to‘qimachilik mahsulotlari tayyorlashning sifati ortadi, natijada xalqimiz turmush farovonligi yanada yuksaladi.

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International journal of theoretical and practical research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2022 Issue: 9

Volume: 2

Published:

30.09.2022

<http://alferganus.uz>

QR-Article

Citation:

Butaboev, M.T., Arziev, M.A. (2022). Human capital is the key value of the digital economy. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 27-36.

Butaboev, M.T., Arziev, M.A. (2022). Human capital is the key value of the digital economy. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 27-36.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7186209>

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UDC 330.101

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7186209

HUMAN CAPITAL IS THE KEY VALUE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Abstract. This article reveals the formation of the spread and development of human capital, its cardinal transformation, which are necessary both for participation in the creation and dissemination of digital technologies, and for their use in the business process in the digital world of knowledge, skills and determining factors of production, entrepreneurship and employment. The article substantiates and recommends the competence model and its indicators in Uzbekistan.

Key words: digital technologies, digital transformation, digital literacy, digital competence, digital consumption, digital security, digital communication, competence model, formation, human capital, project implementation.

ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЙ КАПИТАЛ – КЛЮЧЕВАЯ ЦЕННОСТЬ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье раскрывается формирование распространения и развития человеческого капитала, его кардинальное преобразование, которые необходимы как для участия в создании и распространении цифровых технологий, так и для их использования в бизнес-процессе в цифровом мире знаний, умений и навыков, определяющие факторы производства, предпринимательства и занятости. В статье обоснована и рекомендована модель компетентности и ее индикаторы в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, цифровая трансформация, цифровая грамотность, цифровая компетентность, цифровое потребление, цифровая безопасность, цифровая коммуникация, модель компетентности, формирование, человеческий капитал, реализация проекта.

INSON KAPITI - RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING ASOSIY OMILI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola raqamli texnologiyalarni yaratish va tarqatishda ishtirok etish uchun ham, bilim, ko'nikma va ko'nikmalarning raqamli dunyosida biznes jarayonida foydalanish uchun ham zarur bo'lgan inson kapitalini taqsimlash va rivojlantirish, uning tub o'zgarishini ochib beradi. qobiliyatlar. ishlab chiqarish, tadbirkorlik va bandlik omillarini aniqlash. Maqolada O'zbekistondagi kompetensiya modeli va uning ko'rsatkichlari asoslab berilgan va tavsiya etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, raqamli transformatsiya, raqamli savodxonlik, raqamli kompetensiya, raqamli iste'mol, raqamli xavfsizlik, raqamli aloqa, kompetensiya modeli, shakllantirish, inson kapitali, loyihani amalga oshirish.

Introduction

Usually, human capital is taken to mean abilities, knowledge, skills, and mastered competencies, which together determine the economic productivity of a person (human labor activity is measured in money, a person is seen as an economic resource).

Today, advanced technologies in the field of digitalization and the industrial revolution contribute to the formation of human capital of a fundamentally new quality. As we know, the classical approach to human capital highlights two key components: special and general skills. Until now, special human capital was considered the most valuable, and general was assigned a spatial importance. In the digital economy, however, these roles are changing. It is general skills and literacy (competence) such as strategic thinking, emotional intelligence, adaptability, creativity, the ability to work under uncertainty, the ability to constantly retrain. [1].

The implementation of digital technologies in the digital economy generates demand for specialists with specialized digital competencies, a comprehensive understanding of the field of activity, and knowledge and experience in related fields. The active development of ICT, on the one hand, leads to a reduction of jobs and an increase in wage inequality, and, on the other hand, makes it possible to create fundamentally new in-demand and well-paid professions.

Analysis and results

The competence of human capital will be determined by the ability and readiness to work effectively and efficiently in various socially significant situations on the basis of used key competences. [2].

It is necessary to provide purposeful training to form a systematic set of competencies that will later serve to solve various tasks in the chosen professional field.

A distinction is made between basic, key and professional competences. Competences that are applied throughout a person's life in all spheres of his/her activities are considered to be basic competences. Professional competences include creative thinking, continuous self-development, and productive activities.

The interrelation of competences (Fig.1) determines their systematicness.

Fig.1. Scheme of interconnection of competencies in the system of digital economy competencies.

The analysis of national approaches to the establishment of competences showed that different degrees of detail are allowed based on the tasks of social development.

In Finland, competences are grouped into 4 groups:

1. Ways of thinking, critical thinking, problem solving, decision making;
2. Learning skills;
3. Ability to work and ability to work in a team, tools for work, information literacy;
4. Skills for everyday life: civic literacy, skills for life and career, professional and social responsibility, cultural awareness and competence.

Canada distinguishes between 6 groups of core competencies:

1. Critical thinking;
2. Creativity, innovation, entrepreneurship;
3. Communication;
4. Cooperation;
5. Character education;
6. Civic literacy (the ability to act in fluid and ambiguous circumstances).

The Republic of Korea has developed "cross-cutting competencies for the 21st century. They are six:

- 1) self-management,
- 2) knowledge and information management,
- 3) creative thinking,
- 4) aesthetics and emotionality,
- 5) communication, and
- 6) civic literacy.

The Russian Atlas of New Professions has been developed in Russia, where 11 supraprofessional skills are highlighted:

1. ecological thinking;
2. project management;
3. systems thinking;
4. work with people;
5. work under uncertainty;
6. programming/robotics/artificial intelligence;
7. artistic creativity skills;
8. multilingualism and multiculturalism;
9. interdisciplinary communication;
10. customer-oriented;
11. lean production.

The system of key competences of the European Union is the most interesting from the international experience. According to it 4 qualification levels were developed, each of which has two sublevels:

1. basic level:

- performance of certain operations in a particular competence area under the guidance of a specialist;
- independent performance of certain operations in a specific area of competence and involvement of a specialist if necessary.

2. Intermediate level:

- independently performing certain operations in a specific area of competence and solving emerging problems;
- independent execution of certain operations in a certain competence area according to one's own needs and solving both clearly defined and non-standard tasks for this purpose

3. Advanced Level:

- Guiding others in performing certain operations, demonstrating the capabilities of various technologies, and suggesting different ways to solve problems;

-Performing certain operations in the particular field of competence according to one's own needs and the needs of others, in complex circumstances.

4. Highly specialized level:

- Determining ways to solve complex problems in a specific competency area under limited information, self-development, and making one's own contribution to professional activities;

- solving complex multi-factor problems in a specific area of competence, finding opportunities for self-development, proposing new ideas and processes.

Based on an appropriate set of basic competencies, a system of key digital competencies is formed, extending to the digital economy.

We can consider the main value of improving the quality of human capital to be not just an increase in the volume of knowledge, but the acquisition of specific experience of activity. Digital competences are a system of knowledge, skills, experience, abilities, which are required when using information and communication. Digital competencies are one of the main priorities for the development of basic and specialized skills. Mastering digital competencies facilitates tasks in media and digital environments, media literacy expands opportunities for communication, communication, collaboration, and collaborative problem solving. Effective, systematic accumulation of knowledge as well as critical, professional and flexible thinking are very valuable.

Digital competencies extend to the sphere of digital content creation, including information security software, digital well-being and competence. According to our study, in 2020, the proportion of households connected to the Internet in Uzbekistan is 58.4% (in Fergana region this figure was 51.2%), which is 9.6% more than in 2019 (Fig. 1). In this regard, the problem of digital literacy of the population, both to the professional sphere and at the user level, is acute. [12-18].

Fig. 2. Share of households connected to the Internet in Fergana region compared to the whole territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

It is known that digital literacy is determined, on the contrary, by the knowledge and skills that are necessary for the effective use of digital technologies and resources of the Internet. Digital literacy of the population is formed from digital consumption, digital competencies and digital security. [1,18]

Digital competencies extend to the field of digital content creation, including information security software, digital well-being and competence. Modern digital skills are specific practical skills for using and maintaining digital ecosystems such as 3D, 4D printers, Big Data, block chain, cloud technologies and the Internet of things. According to our study, over 68% of the population of Uzbekistan aged 16 to 70 have ever used a computer and the Internet.

In this regard, the problem of digital literacy of the population is acute, both in the professional sphere and at the user level. [4].

As you know, digital literacy is determined on the contrary by the knowledge and skills that are necessary for the effective use of digital technologies and Internet resources. Digital literacy of the population is formed from digital consumption, digital competencies and digital security. [1,1]

Human digital literacy, i.e. the ability of a person to adapt to the demands of the time on whether he will be able to find the necessary data, transfer them, use the opportunities that digital multimedia provide in the conditions of colossal volumes of information [5].

With the digitalization of the economy, knowledge is subject to depreciation, the more intensively some information is used in production, more and more is counted in the cost of each unit of production goods. Apparently for this reason, many people and even whole countries were not ready for the realities of the digital economy [6].

Currently in Uzbekistan there is a high demand for the use of foreign technology, caused by the low quality of equipment. First, the lack of highly qualified specialists, the competition between countries for a place in the knowledge economy is constantly intensifying. Uzbekistan has not been particularly successful in this field. The country is in a transition phase between a resource economy and a knowledge economy. Secondly, there is low automation of production [7]. By the way, in the next 10-15 years, up to 50% of work operations in the world will be automated. Third, in the new "digital" society, citizenship will be replaced by compulsory identification on government and banking resources on the Internet. All human activity should switch exclusively to an electronic format and paper documents will be decisively excluded. Fourthly, the low level of wages contributes to the outflow of highly skilled personnel in foreign companies, reducing the competitiveness of the economy in the world market and slowing down innovation development in all spheres of activity [8]. Fifth, the high level of monopoly and bureaucracy digital economy breaks the usual models of industrial markets. In a general sense, digitalization is the application of new methods of generating, processing, storage and transmission of data, as well as digital computer technology in the economic activity of society.

Model of Digital Competence of Uzbekistan.

<p>Digital consumption</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet WIFI; - mobile internet, smartphone; - digital devices; - news; - social networks; - public services; - telemedicine; - remote support; - cloud technologies; - Big Data, internet of things (IoT); - block chain;
<p>Digital competencies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - information search; - use of digital devices; - use of social networks; - banking and financial operations; - online shopping; - use of crypto currencies; - use of block chain;
<p>Digital security</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - protection of personal data; - strong login password; - data storage; - environmental protection; - health protection; - device protection; <p>Information literacy - filtering data, information;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - evaluation of data, information; - data and information management; - developing website and application;
<p>information literacy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - filtering data, information; - evaluation of data, information; - data and information management; - developing website and application;
<p>Communication and cooperation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interaction through digital technologies; - cooperation using digital technologies; - online etiquette; -Managing your digital identity; - developing digital content, programming;

In our opinion, the new quality of human capital is manifested in its competence, which is the accumulation of additional skills that ensure life and professional development in the digital environment [9].

Indicators of personnel training on the digital economy in Uzbekistan for the Ferghana region 2020-2023 program based (1 million Uzbek programmers-engineers) [1.4.]

Ensuring the digital economy with competent staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Opening of 30 mono-centers (in districts and villages). b) Training of personnel-programmers on the basis of the Venture Fund in c) Training of 50,000 specialists of the highest category in the field of information technology.
Support for gifted schoolchildren and students in the subjects of mathematics and computer science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Education of 10 thousand gifted students in mathematics, computer science, preparation for grants. b) Training of specialists in web programming.
Increasing digital literacy and competence of the population.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Prepare 1 million people for digital literacy in an online program b) Training of 20 thousand employees in the field of banking and finance for digital competence.

In the national program of Uzbekistan 2020-2023 it is planned to produce 1 million Uzbek programmers-engineers for the digital economy [10]. Based on this program, 30 mono-centers for the education and training of programmers-engineers were organized for the Fergana region in rural areas. Also, 50 thousand specialists in information and qualified personnel will be attracted to work in the field of ICT, as well as 10,000 gifted young men will be mobilized in the subjects of mathematics and physics for training to receive a State grant to study abroad. Here, specialists for Web programming and computer science will be retrained. In addition, 1 million of the population will be trained online to improve digital literacy and competence.

Conclusion. Human capital is one of the most powerful drivers of economic development in general, and in the realities of a digitized world, it becomes even more important. Successful digital transformation in the country is now impossible to imagine without the necessary computer skills within society. That is why Uzbekistan pays great attention to programs to create digital human capital as a result of a system of programs, which certainly contributes to bringing the economy of the Republic to a new level.

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International journal of
theoretical and practical
research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2022 Issue: 9

Volume: 2

Published:

30.09.2022

<http://alferganus.uz>

QR-Article

Citation:

Davlyatova, G. M. (2022). Using the foreign experience of innovative policy. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 37-45.

Davlyatova, G. M. (2022). Innovatsion siyosatning xorij tajribasidan foydalanish. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 37-45.

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<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7186385>

UDC 338.242

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7186385

USING THE FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INNOVATIVE POLICY

Abstract. *In modern conditions, the use of innovations, providing economic growth, is manifested, on the one hand as the main factor in the development of the state, and on the other-as a result of scientific and technological development. The innovative economy is based on innovative activity that ensures the development of the economic system by updating knowledge, innovative factors and technologies as a specific type of economy. The introduction of the experience of developed countries in this direction in the formation of innovation policy in the country creates opportunities for more effective and productive use of them.*

Keywords: *innovation, innovation policy, experience of the USA, Japan, Germany and France.*

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNING XORIJ TAJRIBASIDAN FOYDALANISH

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*Iqtisod fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
"Iqtisodiyot" kafedrasi
Farg'ona politexnika instituti*

Annotatsiya. *Zamonaviy sharoitlarda innovatsiyalardan foydalanish iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlagan holda, bir tomondan davlatning rivojlanishida bosh omil bo'lsa, ikkinchi*

tomondan ilmiy-texnik rivojlanishning natijasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Innovatsion iqtisodiyotning asosi innovatsion faoliyat bo'lib, o'ziga xos iqtisodiyot turi sifatida bilimlarni, innovatsion omillarni va texnologiyalarni yangilash orqali iqtisodiy tizimning rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi. Mamlakatda innovatsion siyosatni shakllantirishda ilg'or mamlakatlarning bu yo'nalishdagi tajribalarini joriy qilish ulardan yana samarali va unumli foydalanish imkoniyatlarini yaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *innovatsiya, innovatsion siyosat, AQSH, Yaponiya, Germaniya va Fransiya tajribasi.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ

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Аннотация. *В современных условиях использование инноваций при обеспечении экономического роста, с одной стороны, является основным фактором развития государства, а с другой стороны, проявляется как результат научно-технического развития. Основой инновационной экономики является инновационная деятельность, которая как уникальный тип экономики обеспечивает развитие экономической системы за счет обновления знаний, инновационных факторов и технологий. Внедрение опыта передовых стран в этом направлении при формировании инновационной политики в стране создает возможности для более эффективного и результативного их использования.*

Ключевые слова: *инновации, инновационная политика, опыт США, Японии, Германии и Франции.*

Kirish

Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash mamlakatni innovatsion rivojlantirishning asosiy va muhim sharti hisoblanadi. Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston Respublikasida barqarorlashuv hukm surayotgan bir paytda iqtisodiyotning chuqur modernizatsiyalashuviga erishmay turib innovatsiyalar diffuziyasiga, ya'ni yangi g'oya, ishlanma va texnologiyalar joriy etilishi va jadal tarqalishiga erishish qiyin. Buning uchun esa, avvalo, ta'lim, ilm-fan va sanoat integratsiyasini ta'minlash, shuningdek, innovatsion mahsulotlarga bo'lgan talabni oshiradigan yangi kompaniyalar tashkil etilishini rag'batlantiruvchi yangi sanoat tarmoqlarini yaratishga ko'maklashadigan bir qator aniq texnik yechimlarni joriy qilish talab etiladi. Bugungi kunda milliy iqtisodiyot oldida turgan dolzarb masalalardan biri ham qisqa muddatda mamlakatning innovatsion rivojlanishiga erishishdir. Aks holda, O'zbekistonning rivojlangan davlatlar qatoridan joy olishi murakkab kechishi aniq. Mazkur masalani ijobiy hal etish uchun keng qamrovli islohotlar olib borish asosiy masallardan biridir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Innovatsion rivojlanish vazirligi mamlakatni innovatsion va ilmiy-texnik rivojlantirish sohasida jamiyat va davlat hayotini

har tomonlama taraqqiy ettirish hamda respublikaning intellektual va texnologik salohiyatini ko‘tarishga qaratilgan yagona davlat siyosatini amalga oshiruvchi davlat boshqaruvi organi bo‘lib, o‘z faoliyati doirasida yuqorida aytib o‘tilgan dolzarb masalalar yechimi borasida aniq belgilangan chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirib kelmoqda. Innovatsion rivojlanish tizimli jarayon bo‘lib, aniq belgilangan chora-tadbirlarni rejaga asosan, ya’ni strategik tarzda amalga oshirishni nazarda tutadi. Bu borada O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil 21 sentyabrdagi PF-5544-son farmoni bilan 2019–2021 yillarda O‘zbekiston Respublikasini innovatsion rivojlantirish strategiyasi, uni amalga oshirish bo‘yicha “Yo‘l xaritasi”, O‘zbekiston Respublikasini 2030 yilgacha innovatsion rivojlantirish maqsadli ko‘rsatkichlarining tasdiqlanishi ayni muddao bo‘ldi. Strategiyaning bosh maqsadi etib mamlakatning xalqaro maydondagi raqobatbardoshligi darajasi va innovatsion jihatdan taraqqiy etganini belgilovchi asosiy omil sifatida inson kapitalini rivojlantirish ko‘rsatilgan bo‘lsa, O‘zbekiston Respublikasining 2030 yilgacha Global innovatsion indeks reytingi bo‘yicha jahonning 50 ta ilg‘or mamlakati qatoriga kirishi esa strategiyaning muhim vazifalaridan biri deb belgilangan.

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlar tahlili

Iqtisodchi olimlar tomonidan “innovatsiya” va “innovatsion jarayon” tushunchalariga o‘ziga xos yondashuvlar bildirilgan. P.F. Druker tomonidan “Innovatsiya – bu tadbirkorlar tomonidan o‘ziga xos vosita bo‘lib, u asosida turli xil xizmat va biznesdagi imkoniyat sifatida foydalanishi mumkin” degan ta’rif berilgan bo‘lsa, R.I.Gimush, F.M.Matmurodovlar esa “Innovatsiya — yangilik va yangilik kiritish degan ma’noni bildiradi. Bu yangilik zamirida yangi tartibni, yangi odatni, yangi uslubni, kashfiyotni tushunish lozim deya ta’rif berishgan. Z.T.Gaibnazarova tomonidan “Innovatsiya - bu kasbiy faoliyatning tubdan tartibga solish, yangi natijalarini yaratish va uni tubdan yangi sifat darajasiga ko‘tarish” degan ta’rif berilgan.

Ushbu ta’riflarning mazmunidan kelib chiqib shuni xulosa qilish mumkinki, innovatsiya- bu yangi kashfiyotlar, yangi jarayonlar, xizmatlar va usullar bo‘lib, u iqtisodiy yoki biznes faoliyatda yuqori darajadagi samara keltirish vazifasini bajaradi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Tadqiqotni olib borishda analiz va sintez usullaridan, tizimli va majmuaviy yondashuv usullardan foydalanilgan.

Tahlillar va natijalar

Ma’lumki, innovatsiya – foydalanish uchun kiritilgan yangi yoki sezilarli darajada yaxshilangan mahsulot (tovar, xizmat) yoki jarayon, sotuvlarning yangicha uslubi yoki ish amaliyotidagi, ish o‘rinlarini tashkil etishdagi va tashqi aloqalarni o‘rnatishdagi yangi tashkiliy uslub hisoblanadi.

“Innovatsiya” atamasi lotincha “novatio”so‘zidan olingan bo‘lib, “yangilanish”(yoki “o‘zgarish”), “in” qo‘shimchasi esa lotinchadan “yo‘nalishida” deb tarjima qilinadi, agar buni yaxlit “Innovatio” ko‘rinishida tarjima qilsak – “o‘zgarishlar yo‘nalishida” deb izohlanadi. Innovation tushunchasi birinchi bo‘lib XIX-asrning ilmiy tadqiqotlarida paydo bo‘ldi. “Innovatsiya” tushunchasi o‘zining yangi hayotini “innovatsion kombinatsiyalar”ni tahlil qilish, iqtisodiy tizimlarning rivojlanishidagi o‘zgarishlar natijasida XX-asrning boshida avstriyalik va amerikalik iqtisodchi Y.Shumpeterning ilmiy ishlarida boshlagan. Shumpeter 1900-

yillarda iqtisodda ushbu termini ilmiy qo'llashga kiritgan dastlabki olimlardan edi. Innovatsiyaga har qanday turdagi yangilik sifatida emas, balki mavjud tizimning samaradorligini jiddiy ravishda oshiradigan omil sifatida qarashimiz lozim. Innovatsiyalarni yaratish, aniqlash va joriy etishga qaratilgan huquqiy, tashkiliy, iqtisodiy, texnologik shart-sharoitlar, qarorlar, usul va uslublar yig'indisi hamda ulardan amaliyotda foydalanish esa innovatsion siyosat debataladi.

Ko'pchilik rivojlangan mamlakatlarda innovatsion siyosatning o'tkazilishi, eng avvalo, muayyan tarmoqlarda innovatsion salohiyatga ega bo'lgan mahalliy ishlab chiqaruvchilarni qo'llab-quvvatlash bilan bog'liq. Bunday siyosat, birinchi navbatda, ishlab chiqarishning texnik jihozlanganligini yaxshilash, tarmoqlar, korxonalarining texnologik darajasini ko'tarish, umuman milliy iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiya qilish va boshqa shu kabilardan iborat bo'lgan qo'shimcha raqobat ustunliklari manbalarini aniqlashga qaratiladi. Ikkinchidan esa, raqobat ustunliklari ko'pincha bozorning yirik raqobatchilarda keltiradigan daromadining kamligi va o'zlashtirish vaqtida ko'lamlarining kichikligi tufayli qiziqish uyg'otmaydigan bo'g'inlarida yaratiladi. Uchinchidan, raqobat ustunliklariga uzluksiz ravishda mablag'lar sarflashni talab etadigan yangi ishlanmalar muntazam mukammalashib borgan taqdirdagina saqlab qolinadi.

Shulardan kelib chiqib, aytish mumkinki, rivojlangan mamlakatlarda davlatning investitsion-innovatsion o'zgarishlar siyosati ilmiy-texnologik tsiklning barcha bosqichlarini rivojlantirish va rag'batlantirishni hisobga olgan holda shakllantirilar ekan. AQSH, Yaponiya, Germaniya va Frantsiya tajribasining ko'rsatishicha, mamlakatning barqaror rivojlanishiga erishining muhim omillari investitsiyalar va innovatsion ishlanmalar hisoblanar ekan, mana shuning uchun ham bu mamlakatlarda investitsion jarayonni faollashtirish uchun sharoitlar yaratib berish vazifalari, xususan innovatsion strategiyasini yaratish, milliy iqtisodiyotning preferentsial tarmoqlariga selektiv yordam ko'rsatish, xususiy va qarz investitsiyalarini jalb etish va joylashtirish hamda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri va portfel' investitsiyalar o'rtasidagi munosabat masalalari birinchi darajali bo'lib hisoblanadi.

Jahon tajribasini o'rganib quyidagicha xulosa qilish mumkinki, iqtisodiyotni innovatsion rivojlantirishning investitsion omili ichki raqobatning rivojlanishini kuchaytiradi, mahalliy iste'mol bozorini kengaytiradi, yangi eksportga yo'naltirilgan tarmoqlarni rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratadi, iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiya qilish uchun moddiy baza bo'lib xizmat qiladi. O'zbekiston sharoitlarida bunday samarali investitsion-innovatsion siyosatni qo'llash, bizning fikrimizcha, tarmoqlarning eksport salohiyatini kengaytirish va diversifikatsiya qilishga, import o'rnini bosuvchi ishlab chiqarishlarni rivojlantirishga, inftratuzilmani, transport va aloqa vositalarini kengaytirishga yordam beradi, bu esa o'z navbatida, mahalliy tovarlar va texnologiyalarni tashqi bozorlarga olib chiqish jarayoni va ishlab chiqarishni tashkil etishning ilg'or shakllarini o'zlashtirilishi bilan uzviy bog'liq.

Xorijiy mamlakatlarda (AQSH, Yaponiya mamlakatlari) maqsadli investitsiya dasturlari, soliq va investitsiya imtiyozlari, jadallashtirilgan amortizatsiya siyosati kabi moliyaviy oqimlarni boshqarish vositalaridan foydalanish orqali amalga oshirilayotgan innovatsion jarayonlar mamlakatning makroiqtisodiy rivojlanishiga samarali ta'sir

ko'rsatmoqda. Masalan, AQSH va Yaponiyada iqtisodiy o'sishni jadallashtirish va iqtisodiyotni barqarorlashtirish maqsadlarida soliq islohotlari o'tkazildi va amortizatsiya chegirmalari tizimi takomillashtirildi. Jadallashtirilgan amortizatsiya siyosati ishlab chiqarish apparatini yangilash negizida raqobatbardosh tarmoqlar rivojlanishini tezlashtiradi. Bunda yaratilgan amortizatsiya fondi ish haqi manbai sifatida foydalaniladigan joriy daromadlar fondidan takror ishlab chiqariladigan kapital fondiga aydanadi va u ayniqsa inqiroz sharoitida iqtisodiyot uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Chet mamlakatlar tajribasi shundan dalolat bermoqdaki, yirik moliya-sanoat birlashmalari qo'llab-quvvatlash ham innovatsion rivojlanish yo'nalishlari qatoridan o'rin olgan. O'zining iqtisodiy mohiyatiga ko'ra, moliya-sanoat birlashmalari yirik moliya va sanoat kapitaliga ega yuridik shaxslarning birlashuvini ifodalaydi. Moliya-sanoat birlashmalari iqtisodiyotning innovatsion yo'lga qadam qo'yishiga yordam beradi, ilmiy-texnik yutuqlarni amalga oshirish uchun maqbul sharoitlar yaratadi, mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga barqarorlik va boshqaruvchanlik baxsh etadi.

Ta'kidlash joizki, asosiy kapitalning o'sib borishida nisbatan yirik korporatsiyalarning ulushi katta bo'ladi, ular o'rtasida qo'shib ketish va yutilish hisobiga yuzaga kelgan eng yiriklari alohida ajralib turadi. Shuningdek, bunda yirik korxonalar bilan alohida tadbirkorlarning innovatsion g'oyalarini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi kichik biznes o'rtasidagi kooperatsion aloqalarni kuchaytirishga yordam beruvchi xo'jalik va moliyaviy mexanizmlarning yaratilishi iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishi hisoblanadi. Konsolidatsiyalashtirilgan kapitalni davlat tomonidan tartibga solishning samaradorligi bozor yo'nalishidagi amaliy-tadqiqotchilik markazlarining rivojlanishida o'z ifodasini topadi.

Iqtisodiyotni innovatsion tavsifda rivojlantirishning yana bir yo'nalishi mintaqaviy rivojlanish sohasida uzoq muddatli siyosatni amalga oshirish hisoblanadi. Bunday siyosat Italiyada muvaffaqiyat bilan olib borilmoqda va u o'zaro bog'liq vazifalarning yechimini topishga, xususan, investitsiyalar va yangiliklarni joriy etish asosida raqobat ustunliklarini yaratishga qaratiladi. Bu yerda mintaqaviy rivojlanish dasturini amalga oshirishda alohida mintaqalarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, sanoat qudratining rivojlanish darajasi, yuqori malakali kadrlar va ilmiy-tadqiqot markazlarining mavjudligi e'tiborga olinadi. Bu mintaqada ilg'or ilmiy markazlarni va Italiya iqtisodiyotida samarali faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan nisbatan rivojlangan va raqobatbardosh tarmoqlarda yo'ldosh ishlab chiqarishlarni yaratishga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Bunday siyosat alohida mintaqalarning rivojlanishidagi notekislik va qoloqlikni bartaraf etishga imkon beradi. Italiya tajribasi shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, mintaqalar iqtisodiyotini tartibga solish tarmoq va hududiy ustuvorliklarni o'stirish tamoyiliga rioya etilgan shroitda ancha samarali hisoblanadi. Mazkur holatda eng kuchli raqobat ustunligiga ega tarmoq yuqori darajada murakkab talab yaratadi va ham ichki, ham tashqi bozor uchun sanoat ahamiyatiga molik mahsulotlar va xizmatlar yetkazib beruvchi sifatida chiqadi. Bunday siyosat yuritish orqali iqtisodiy jihatdan nisbatan qoloq mintaqalarni ularning hududida bozorga oraliq mahsulotlar yetkazib beradigan aralash tarmoqlarni joylashtirish hamda ularning xususiy ilmiy-maorif bazasini, tadqiqot laboratoriyalarini barpo etish yo'li bilan iqtisodiy rivojlanishini jadallashtiradi, bu esa markaziy hokimiyatning qarz va subsidiyalaridan foydalanishga qaraganda ko'proq samara keltiradi. O'zbekiston sharoitida davlatning

bunday qo'llab-quvvatlash tajribasidan foydalanish, bizning fikrimizcha, alohida hududlarning teng rivojlanishiga respublika sanoati aralash tarmoqlarida innovatsion faoliyatni faollashtirishga yordam ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Xorijda milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning muhim yo'nalishlaridan yana biri fiskal siyosat o'tkazishdir, uning yordamida davlat mamlakatning makroiqtisodiy ahvoriga ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Modomiki, tartibga solishning mazkur turi bo'yicha qabul qilingan chora-tadbirlar qisqa vaqt oralig'ida o'z natijalarini berar ekan, demak u ancha ta'sirchan usul hisoblanadi.

Germaniyaning fiskal tartibga solish sohasidagi tajribasi shundaki, bunda davlat federal yerlarning soliq salohiyatini tenglashtirish davomida transfertlardan foydalanadi hamda "jon boshiga" to'g'ri keladigan daromadlarni tenglashtirishda esa "aks transfert"larni faol qo'llaydi.

Fiskal tartibga solishning yapon tajribasi yuqori texnologiyalarni qo'llashning, ya'ni model byudjetlarni tuzish (alohida prefektura va munitsipalitetlar uchun) va mintaqaviy rivojlanishning tabiiy-iqlim, institutsional, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy xususiyatlarini aks ettiruvchi modifikatsiya koeffitsienti yordamida ularni kelgusida korrektirovka qilishning klassik namunasi bo'lib hisoblanadi.

AQSHning byudjet-soliq siyosatida, xususan mahalliy hokimiyat organlarining moliyaviy asosini mustahkamlash sohasida olib boradigan faoliyatida ko'plab ijobiy tomonlarni ta'kidlab o'tish mumkin: mahalliy soliqlarni belgilashda ko'proq erkinlik berish, transfert yordam ko'rsatish dasturida qat'iy asoslab berish orqali xarajatlarni davlat bilan ulushli asosda amalga oshirish. Kanadada byudjet-soliq tartiboti sohasida asosiy e'tibor hokimiyatning quyi pog'onasi uchun soliqlarni pasaytirishni ham o'z ichiga olgan dasturiy-maqсадli tartibga solish usullari birikmasiga qaratiladi. Barqarorlashtiruvchi fondlarga ega mamlakatlarning investitsion-innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirish tajribasi ham katta qiziqish uyg'otadi. Maxsus umummilliy va mintaqaviy barqarorlashtiruvchi fondlarni yaratish va ishga tushirish bo'yicha milliy loyihalar shaklida amalga oshiriladigan iqtisodiyotni byudjet-soliq yuzasidan tartibga solish mexanizmiga ega mamlakatlar qatorida quyidagilarni sanab o'tish mumkin: Davlat neft fondiga ega – Norvegiya, CHili – Mis barqarorlashtiruvchi fondi, AQSH (Alyaska shtati) – Kelajak avlodni qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun Jamg'arma fondi va Rezervdagi byudjet fondi, Quvayt – Umumiy rezerv fondi, Kelajak avlod rezerv fondi va Investitsiya fondi, shuningdek Rossiyada – Rezerv fondi va RF Milliy farovonlik fondiga ega.

Maxsus fondlarning mablag'laridan uzoq muddat davomida milliy byudjet barqarorligini ta'minlashda va strategik xom ashyo resurslari bahosi keskin o'zgargan sharoitlarda qisqa muddatli davrlarda byudjet xarajatlarini qo'llab-quvvatlashda, istiqbolda iqtisodiyotning innovatsion va investitsion rivojlanishini kuchaytirishni ta'minlashda foydalaniladi. Mazkur fondlar iqtisodiy rivojlanishni harakatga keltiruvchi, iqtisodiy jihatdan qoloq mintaqalarga, iqtisodiyotning zaif rivojlangan tarmoqlariga samarali ta'sir ko'rsata oladigan kuchlar tavsifiga ega faoliyatning vazifalari va yo'nalishlarida ko'zda tutilgan muayyan maqsadlar asosida yaratiladi.

Xulosa

Umuman olganda, bozor iqtisodiyoti rivojlangan davlatlarda mamlakatda investitsion va innovatsion jarayonlarni davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashning

iqtisodiy chora-tadbirlari bozor sub'ektlari xo'jalik faoliyatiga ta'sir ko'rsatishning samarali usuli bo'lib hisoblanadi, u muhim tarmoqlarni rekonstruktsiya qilish va yangilarini yaratishni jadallashtiradi, shuningdek umuman milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa qilish mumkinki, har bir mamlakatning innovatsion strategiyalari turlicha bo'lib, bu tarixiy va milliy rivojlanish xususiyatlari, sanoatning va texnologik bazaning taraqqiy etish darajasi va boshqa omillarga bog'liq holda shakllantiriladi. Milliy innovatsion tizimni yaratishning yagona universal retsepti mavjud emas, chunki davlatlarning to'g'ri va samarali yagona strategiyasi ham bo'lmaydi. Shunga qaramay, bir-biridan ajralib turuvchi innovatsion tizimlar ba'zi bir umumiy xususiyatlarga ham ega bo'lishi mumkin, shuning uchun ham nisbatan rivojlangan raqobatbardosh mamlakatlarning muvaffaqiyatli texnologik tajribasidan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi.

Innovatsiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha xorij tajribasidan foydalanish hisobiga 2030 yilga kelib quyidagi natijalarga erishish mumkin:

- 2030 yilga kelib aholi jon boshiga to'g'ri keladigan YaIM miqdori oshadi;
- muhandislar, iqtisodchilar va menejerlar bozorda ustunlik qila boshlaydi ;
- ishsizlik darajasi kamaytiriladi;
- yangi g'oya va yangilik beruvchilar soni ortadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. "Iqtisodiyotni yanada rivojlantirish va iqtisodiy siyosat samaradorligini oshirishning qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 8 yanvardagi PF-5614-son Farmoni.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlari va sohalariga innovatsiyalarni joriy etish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish bo'yicha qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida"gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil, 7maydagi PQ-3698-sonli qarori.
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International journal of
theoretical and practical
research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2022 Issue: 9 Volume: 2

Published: 30.09.2022

<http://alferganus.uz>

Citation:

Pyosov, A.A. (2022). German experience of state support of export of industrial products. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 46-56.

Илёсов, А.А. (2022). Саноат маҳсулотлари экспортини давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлашнинг германия тажрибаси. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 46-56.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7187496>

QR-Article

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UDC 339.564

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7187496

**GERMAN EXPERIENCE OF STATE SUPPORT OF EXPORT OF
INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTS**

Abstract. *The article analyzes the German experience of state support for the export of industrial products. The purpose of the study is to develop, based on the analysis, proposals and recommendations for the further development of exports of industrial products in our country. The study used methods of comparative analysis, grouping and synthesis.*

Key words: *information and consulting system, financial mechanisms, mechanisms to support the export of industrial products, insurance, organizational and economic mechanisms.*

**САНОАТ МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИ ЭКСПОРТИНИ ДАВЛАТ ТОМОНИДАН
ҚЎЛЛАБ-ҚУВВАТЛАШНИНГ ГЕРМАНИЯ ТАЖРИБАСИ**

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Аннотация. Мақолада саноат маҳсулотлари экспортини давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлашнинг Германия тажрибаси таҳлил қилинган. Тадқиқот мақсади таҳлил асосида мамлакатимизда саноат маҳсулотлари экспортини янада ривожлантириши юзасидан таклиф ва тавсиялар ишлаб чиқишдан иборат. Тадқиқотда қиёсий таҳлил, гуруҳлаш ва синтез усулларидан фойдаланилган.

Калит сўзлар: ахборот-маслаҳат тизими, молиявий механизмлар, саноат маҳсулотлари экспортини қўллаб-қувватлаш механизмлари, суғурталаш, ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмлар.

НЕМЕЦКИЙ ОПЫТ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ЭКСПОРТА ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ

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Аннотация. В статье анализируется немецкий опыт государственной поддержки экспорта промышленной продукции. Цель исследования - на основе анализа разработать предложения и рекомендации по дальнейшему развитию экспорта промышленной продукции в нашей стране. В исследовании использовались методы сравнительного анализа, группировки и синтеза.

Ключевые слова: информационно-консультационная система, финансовые механизмы, механизмы поддержки экспорта промышленной продукции, страхование, организационно-экономические механизмы.

Кириш

Ривожланган мамлакатлар саноат маҳсулотлари экспортини қўллаб-қувватлаш чоралари ва механизмларини қўллаш тажрибасини ўрганиш миллий экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимларидан фойдаланишни такомиллаштириш имконини берганлиги сабабли самарали халқаро тажриба сифатида алоҳида қизиқиш уйғотмоқда.

Бозор иқтисодиёти ривожланган мамлакатларда ташқи иқтисодий фаолиятни тартибга солишда мавжуд экспорт салоҳиятидан самарали фойдаланишни таъминлашга йўналтирилган миллий экспортчиларни рағбатлантириш усуллари алоҳида ўрин тутати. Бу ўринда Япония тажрибасини ўрганиш муҳим ўрин тутати.

Хорижий давлатларда қўлланилаётган давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш чоралари саноат маҳсулотлари экспортини қўллаб-қувватлашнинг хилма-хил, турли туман ташкилий-молиявий механизмларни ўз ичига олади.

Экспортнинг миллий давлат суғуртаси ҳукуматнинг умумий иқтисодий сиёсати, мамлакатнинг иқтисодий ҳаётда бевосита иштирок этишига бўлган

муносабати, миллий суғурта тизимининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари ва бошқа баъзи омилларга боғлиқ ҳолда турли хил ташкилий шаклларга эга. Экспортни суғурталаш давлат ташкилотлари ёки вазирликлар (масалан, АҚШ, Буюк Британия, Япония), ҳукумат номидан ва унинг топшириғига асосан хусусий суғурта компаниялари ёки банклар томонидан (Германия, Австрия), жамоат ташкилотлари ёки фондлар (Швеция, Финляндия), давлат мулки иштирокидаги молиявий институтлар томонидан амалга оширилади (Франция, Испания).

Мавзуга оид адабиётларнинг таҳлили

Илёсов А. (2020) рақамли иқтисодиётда рақамли ишлаб чиқариш ва саноат маҳсулотларини экспорт қилишдаги айрим муаммоларга эътибор қаратилган [1].

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Илёсов, А. А. (2020). Саноат маҳсулотлари экспортининг мамлакат ва ҳудудий даражадаги таҳлили асосида айрим амалий таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган [7].

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Тадқиқот методологияси.

Тадқиқотда тизимли таҳлил, синтез, статистик гуруҳлаш, эксперт баҳолари ва бошқа усуллардан фойдаланилган.

Таҳлил ва натижалар.

Германия экспортини қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимининг асосий хусусиятлари юқори барқарорлик ва самарадорлик, федерал, минтақавий даражада ривожланган институционал тузилма ва замонавий қўллаб-қувватлаш воситаларининг мавжудлиги ҳисобланади.

Германияда экспортни давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлашнинг энг муҳим элементи молиявий характердаги чора-тадбирлар бўлиб, биринчи навбатда, кредитлаш, суғурталаш ва давлат кафолатларини бериш сифатида намоён бўлади. Ушбу масалалар бўйича қарорларни Германиянинг турли вазирлик ва идоралари вакилларида иборат Вазирликлараро қўмита қабул қилади.

Амалда Германияда экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимлари қуйидаги молиявий чораларни қўлламоқда:

- хорижда немис фирмалари экспорт кредитлари ва инвестицияларини суғурталаш;
- экспортёрларни қўшилган қиймат солиғини тўлашдан озод қилиш;
- саноат тармоқларини бевосита ва билвосита субсидиялаш;
- илмий тадқиқот ва тажриба конструкторлик ишланмалари (ИТТКИ – НИОКР)ни молиявий қўллаб-қувватлаш.

Германия экспортини бевосита молиялаштириш асосан ихтисослаштирилган давлат кредит ташкилотлари, шунингдек, хусусий банклар томонидан амалга оширилади. Кичик ва ўрта бизнес экспорт ва лойиҳавий молиялаштиришга ихтисослашган хусусий банклар консорциуми АКА (<https://www.akabankde.de>) ва KfW давлат банк гуруҳи (<https://www.kfw.de/kfw.de>) мамлакатдаги этакчи экспорт кредит ташкилотлари ҳисобланади.

Германияда экспортни молиялаштиришнинг зарурий шарти дунёдаги экспорт кредитларини суғурталашга ихтисослашган энг йирик суғурта компанияси Euler Hermes Kreditversicherungs-AG даги (<https://www.eulerhermes.de>) - Euler Hermes - ҳисобланади. Euler Hermes бир вақтнинг ўзида ўз фаолиятини консорциумда этакчи консалтинг фирмаларидан бири, консалтинг ва аудиторлик соҳасида профессионал хизматларини таклиф этувчи компаниялар халқаро тармоғидаги Германия филиали – PricewaterhouseCoopers билан бирга олиб боради.

Ушбу ваколатли компаниялар қуйидагилар учун жавобгардирлар:

- немис экспортёрларининг буюртмаларини амалда сиёсий ва иқтисодий таваккалчилик нуқтаи назаридан таклиф қилинаётган битимларнинг ишончлилигини дастлабки текшириш;
- Вазирликлараро қўмита доирасида уни муҳокама қилиш учун комплекс буюртма тайёрлаш;
- суғурта битимини расмийлаштириш;
- суғурта қилинган экспорт операциялари давомида немис экспортчисини кузатиб бориш;
- суғурта ҳодисаси юз берганда суғурта пули тўланишини таъминлаш.

Euler Hermes суғурта учун маблағларни давлат бюджетидан олади. Ушбу маблағлар ҳисобидан суғурта ҳодисаси бўйича тўловлар тўланади. Консорциум ўз фаолияти учун тўловларни суғурта полиси эгалари томонидан буюртмалар топширилгандан кейин текшириш учун олинадиган йиғимлар ҳисобига амалга оширади. Йиғимлар суммаси битимнинг умумий миқдоридан келиб чиқиб ҳисобланади ва бу суғурта қопламаси миқдорига боғлиқ эмас.

Йиғимлар битим суммаси билан бир қаторда, қуйидаги параметрлар билан аниқланади:

- мамлакат категорияси;
- битимнинг давомийлиги (унга қўйиладиган талаблар);
- харидорнинг статуси (хусусий ёки давлат);
- банк кафолати мавжудлиги ёки йўқлиги.

Экспортни қўллаб-қувватлашнинг зарур чора-тадбирлари ва процедуралари "Экспорт кафолатларини қабул қилиш бўйича кўрсатмалар" (немисча: "Gesetz zur Uebernahme von Sicherheits- und Gewährleistungen im Ausfuhrgeschaef")да ўз

аксини топган, унга мувофиқ барча чора-тадбирлар (тақдим этилган кафолат ва кафилликлар) мамлакат манфаатлари ва амалдаги халқаро ҳуқуқ нормаларига зид бўлмаслиги керак.

Кўрсатмаларга мувофиқ, Германия давлати иқтисодий ва сиёсий рисклардан ҳимоялаш учун кафиллик ва кафолатлар беради. Асосий иқтисодий рискларга хусусий қарздорларнинг банкротлиги ёки қарзни тўлаш муддати белгиланган санадан кейин олти ой ичида тўланмаслик эҳтимоллиги киради.

Агар немис экспортчисининг контрагенти хусусий компания бўлса, экспорт кафолатлари тақдим этилади. Контрагент давлат, муниципал ва бошқа давлат идоралари томонидан кафолатланган бўлса эса, экспорт кафилликлари тақдим этилади. Хусусий компания давлат компаниясидан фарқли ўлароқ, тўловга қобилиятсизлик ҳолатида унга нисбатан банкротлик таомили қўлланилиши мумкин.

Экспортчилар учун товарларни жўнатишдан олдин юзага келиши мумкин бўлган ишлаб чиқариш хатарлари ва уларни жўнатишдан кейин юзага келадиган экспорт хатарлари суғурталанади. Ишлаб чиқариш хавфини суғурталашда, экспортёр шартномани ишлаб чиқариш босқичида муддатидан олдин бекор қилинган ёки тегишли иқтисодий ва сиёсий сабабларга кўра тайёр, аммо жўнатилмаган товарларнинг мавжудлиги натижасида этказилган ишлаб чиқариш харажатларини қоплаш кўзда тутилади. Экспорт хавфи юзага келганда, товарларнинг суғурта қилинган шартномавий қиймати қопланиши ва экспорт кредити бўйича тегишли фоизлар тўланиши таъминланади. Кредит ташкилотларига берилган экспорт кредитлари бўйича кафолатлар ва кафилликлар тақдим этилади.

Немис экспортёрларининг рисклари учун кафолатлар ва кафилликларнинг тўртта асосий шакли кўзда тутилган:

- бир марталик қоплаш (битта экспорт шартномаси бўйича ва битта хорижий контрагент учун);
- даврий (қайта тикланадиган) экспорт кафолати ёки кафиллиги кўринишидаги бир неча маротаба қоплаш (қисқа муддатли тўловлар асосида битта контрагентга доимий этказиб бериш);
- кафолатлар ёки кафилликлар беришнинг соддалаштирилган тартиби ва суғурта мукофотларини тўлаш учун янада қулай шарт-шароитлар билан экспортни бир марталик қоплаш (қисқа муддатли тўловлар асосида турли мамлакатлардаги кўплаб контрагентларга доимий этказиб бериш);
- махсус қоплаш (бу тур алоҳида муҳокама қилинади, масалан, лизинг битимлари ва қурилиш хизматларини қоплаш).

Экспортга қўмаклашиш миллий тизимининг ташкилий ядроси федерал даражада учта ташкилот – Ташқи ишлар вазирлиги (<http://www.auwaertiges-amt.de>), Иқтисодиёт ва энергетика вазирлиги (<http://www.bmwi.de>) ва хорижий савдо палаталаридан иборат.

Анъанавий равишда, экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш соҳасида молиявий институтлар ва жамоат ташкилотлари – Германия Савдо-саноат палаталари уюшмаси (ДИНК, <http://www.dihk.de>), Германия саноат федерал иттифоқи ва унга

кирувчи тадбиркорларнинг тармоқ иттифоқлари, Немис экспортёрларининг федерал иттифоқи, дунёнинг алоҳида минтақаларида немис иштирокчиларига ахборот ва таҳлилий ёрдам кўрсатишга ихтисослашган Германия иқтисодиёти кўмиталари муҳим рол ўйнайди. Германия экспортини қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимининг марказий ташкилоти сифатида Германия Федерал иқтисодиёт ва энергетика вазирлиги гавдаланади.

Иқтисодиёт ва Энергетика вазирлигининг ташқи иқтисодий фаолиятга кўмаклашиш соҳасидаги вазифалари:

- ташқи иқтисодий сиёсат, савдо-инвестициявий ҳамкорликнинг мамлакат ва тармоқ устуворликларини ишлаб чиқиш, ушбу соҳада хорижий давлатлар билан шартномаларни (хусусан, давлатлараро ҳамкорлик) тайёрлаш ва амалга ошириш;
- ташқи иқтисодий фаолиятни ривожлантириш бўйича Германия Trade & Invest давлат агентлиги фаолиятини бошқариш ва назорат қилиш;
- давлат мақсадли экспорт дастурлари ва ташаббусларини режалаштириш ва амалга ошириш;
- немис кичик ва ўрта корхоналарининг экспортини қўллаб-қувватлаш бўйича махсус дастурларни тайёрлаш;
- хорижий Ташқи савдо палаталари фаолиятини молиялаштириш (ДИНК билан биргаликда).

Германияда экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш миллий тизимининг асосий институтлари 1-расмда кўрсатилган.

Иқтисодиёт ва Энергетика вазирлигининг муҳим ваколати ташқи иқтисодий фаолиятни федерал ва федерал ерлар даражасида қўллаб-қувватлаш соҳасидаги йирик дастурлар ва ташаббусларнинг амалга оширилишини мувофиқлаштириш ва мониторинг қилишдир. Вазирлик, шунингдек, экспортга кўмаклашиш билан шуғулланадиган федерал институтлар фаолиятини мувофиқлаштириш учун жавобгардир.

Ҳозирги вақтда Германиянинг ташқи савдо палаталари (ВТП) мамлакатнинг хориждаги классик савдо ваколатхоналари роли ва функцияларини бажаради. Улар бежизга Германия экспортини давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимидаги учта асосий институтлардан бири ҳисобланмайди. Расмий маълумотларга кўра, 80 дан ортиқ мамлакатларда Германиянинг ташқи савдо палатасининг 120 дан ортиқ хорижий ваколатхоналари мавжуд.

1-расм. Германияда экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимининг асосий институтлари

Германиянинг ташқи савдо палаталари хорижда қуйидаги асосий вазифаларни бажарадилар (2-расм):

биринчидан, улар Германия иқтисодиётининг ташқи иқтисодий манфаатларини ифодалайди ва ҳукумат номидан қабул қилувчи мамлакат билан савдо-иқтисодий алоқаларни ривожлантиришда бевосита қатнашиши керак;

бу вазифа аслида бошқа қўллаб мамлакатларнинг давлат савдо ваколатхоналарига (миссия) юкланган вазифага ўхшайди;

иккинчидан, палаталарнинг энг муҳим вазифаси Германия фирмаларига уларнинг ташқи бозорга чиқишига ёки бизнесни ривожлантиришга кўмаклашиш мақсадида бизнес хизматларини кўрсатишдир.

Германия ташқи савдо палаталарининг миллий экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш соҳасидаги устувор вазифалари

- ҳамкор мамлакатларнинг иқтисодиёти ва ташқи иқтисодий фаолияти, инвестиция ва экспорт салоҳияти таҳлили;
- ташқи иқтисодий ва савдо сиёсатидаги ўзгаришлар тўғрисида бошқарув органларига мунтазам равишда маълумотларни тайёрлаш;
- давлат мақсадли лойиҳа ва ташаббусларини амалга оширишда қатнашиш;
- Немис корхоналарига ахборот-маслаҳат ва юридик хизматлар кўрсатиш;
- ички бозорнинг импорт ва инвестицион талабларига оид тадқиқотлар олиб бориш;
- қабул қилувчи мамлакат давлат бошқарув органлари билан ҳамкорликда Немис экспортёр ва инвесторлари манфаатларини ҳимоялаш (лоббिलाш);
- ТИФни давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимининг бошқа институтлари вакиллари билан қўшма тадбирларни амалга ошириш (пиар компаниялар, имиджни ошириш тадбирлари ва ҳ.к.);
- Германия расмийлари ва бизнес соҳаси вакиллари ташрифларини ташкил қилиш ва кузатиб бориш;
- турли проумоторлик тадбирларини ташкил қилиш ва ўтказишда экспортёрларни қўллаб-қувватлаш.

2-расм. Германия ташқи савдо палаталарининг вазифалари

Германия Trade & Invest давлат агентлиги (GTAI, <http://www.gtai.de>) ташқи иқтисодий фаолият миллий иштирокчиларига самарали ахборот-маслаҳат ёрдами тизимининг марказий бўғини ҳисобланади.

Германия Trade & Invest давлат агентлигининг асосий манбаи агентликнинг барча йирик ёки истиқболли ҳамкор давлатлардаги кучли вакиллик тармоғидир, бу ерга барча вазифаларни бажариш учун зарур малакага эга бўлган тажрибали мутахассислар юборилади. Бугунги кунда дунёда GTAInинг 50 га яқин вакиллик идоралари мавжуд.

GTAI, шунингдек, Германиянинг миллий экспортчиларини қўллаб-қувватловчи энг йирик ахборот ресурси, iXPOS Интернет-порталининг (<http://www.ixpos.de>) маълуми сифатида ишлайди. Ушбу портал соҳадаги барча етакчи ваколатли ташкилотларнинг экспортни ривожлантириш воситалари ҳақидаги маълумотларни бирлаштиради. Умуман олганда, Германияда экспорт фаолиятини ривожлантириш соҳасида уч юздан ортиқ турли ташкилотлар фаолият кўрсатмоқда.

Германиянинг экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш тизими, ташкилий нуқтаи назардан, функциялар, ваколатлар ва мувофиқлаштириш механизмларини аниқ тақсимлайдиган ягона механизмдир. Ташқи иқтисодий фаолият соҳасидаги барча муҳим тадбирлар ва ташаббуслар (шу жумладан минтақавий миқёсда амалга ошириладиган тадбирлар) Иқтисодиёт ва энергетика федерал вазирлиги, айрим

ҳолларда эса мамлакат ташқи ишлар вазирлиги билан келишилган бўлиши керак.

Хулоса ва таклифлар

Хулоса қилиб айтганда, ҳозирги вақтда ривожланган мамлакатларда миллий экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш учун жуда мукамал тузилма яратилган ва муваффақиятли фаолият кўрсатмоқда. У бир хил эмас, турли давлатларда умумий хусусиятлар билан бирга фарқли томонлари ҳам мавжуд. Ҳар бир мамлакатда миллий экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимини такомиллаштириш жараёни давом этмоқда, бунинг натижасида экспортни қўллаб-қувватлашнинг умумий воситалари жорий этилиб, миллий фарқлар, қоида тариқасида халқаро ва минтақавий иқтисодий интеграция доирасида қабул қилинган мажбуриятлар таъсири остида ўзгартирилади.

Саноат маҳсулотлари экспортининг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмлари қўлланилишининг таҳлили куйидаги хулосалар чиқаришга имкон беради:

Ривожланган мамлакатларда давлат томонидан экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш ташқи иқтисодий сиёсатнинг муҳим таркибий қисми ҳисобланади.

Замонавий иқтисодиётда маҳсулотлар экспортини амалга ошириш ва экспорт ҳажмини ошириш учун бир қатор чоралар ва воситалардан фойдаланиш мумкин, бу эса экспорт қилувчилар учун қулай муҳитни яратишдан тортиб, юқори технологияли экспорт ишлаб чиқаришни ривожлантиришни рағбатлантириш чораларига қадар амалга оширилади. Деярли ҳар бир мамлакатда экспортни қўллаб-қувватлайдиган махсус институтлар мавжуд.

Турли давлатларнинг миллий экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимлари бир-биридан сезиларли даражада фарқ қилади. Бу экспортни давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш тизимлари асосан экспортёрларнинг эҳтиёжларига йўналтирилган бўлиб, улар асосан маълум бир давлатнинг экспорти хусусиятлари, шунингдек молия бозорининг ривожланиш даражаси каби бир қатор омилларга боғлиқ.

Давлатлар миллий экспортёрларга экспортни ривожлантиришга ёрдам берадиган кўплаб молиявий маҳсулотларни таклиф этадилар. Шу билан бирга, баъзи мамлакатларда экспорт кредитлари, кафолатлар ва суғурта билан таъминлайдиган экспортни қўллаб-қувватловчи йирик институтлар ташкил этилган, бошқаларида эса экспортни қўллаб-қувватлаш вазифасини бажарувчи давлат иштирокидаги экспорт кредитлари беришга ихтисослашган банклар ва экспортнинг классик кредит агентликлари каби бир нечта институтлар мавжуд.

Етакчи экспортёр-давлатлар томонидан экспортни қўллаб-қувватлашнинг номолиявий усулларига жиддий эътибор берилмоқда. Экспортни ахборот билан таъминлаш ва маҳсулотни реклама қилиш муаммосини ҳал қилиш учун мамлакатда экспортни ривожлантириш бўйича махсус агентликлар ташкил этилган бўлиб, улар экспорт қилувчи мамлакатда ҳам, хорижда ҳам кенг ваколатхоналар тармоғи орқали фаолият олиб боради.

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<http://alferganus.uz>

Citation:

Muminova, E. A., Uraimzhonov, A.R. (2022). Improvement of transformation processes development mechanisms of electro technical industrial enterprises and expansion of their economic potential in the field in Uzbekistan. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 57-65.

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Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7187523>

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UDC 620.9

IMPROVEMENT OF TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES DEVELOPMENT MECHANISMS OF ELECTRO TECHNICAL INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND EXPANSION OF THEIR ECONOMIC POTENTIAL IN THE FIELD IN UZBEKISTAN

Abstract. *This article discusses the issues of improving the development of transformation processes at industrial enterprises. The purpose of this study is to assess the state of the electronic industry in Uzbekistan and to propose solutions for its development. According to the results of the study, today the electronic industry of Uzbekistan has the largest number of employees in the industrial group of the region. In addition, net product and business income are growing rapidly in this sector. In particular, in the research work, analyses were made on the creation of new production capacities in the electrical industry in 2021–2022 and the launch of investment projects that will be implemented within the framework of the production diversification program.*

Keywords: *industry, transformation, economy, mechanism, method, development, electronics, electrical equipment, Uzbekistan.*

ELEKTROTEXNIKA SANOATI KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI O'ZGARTIRISH JARAYONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA ULARNING O'ZBEKISTONDAGI IQTISODIY SALOHIYATINI KENGAYTIRISH

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Annotasiya. *Ushbu maqolada sanoat korxonalarining transformatsion jarayonlarini rivojlantirishni takomillashtirish masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi O'zbekistondagi elektron sanoatning holatini baholash va uni rivojlantirish bo'yicha yechimlarni taklif qilishdan iborat. O'rganish natijalariga ko'ra, bugungi kunda O'zbekiston elektron sanoati mintaqaning sanoat guruhida eng ko'p xodimlarga ega; Bundan tashqari, ushbu sohada sof mahsulot va biznes daromadlari tez sur'atlar bilan o'sib bormoqda. Jumladan, tadqiqot ishida 2021-2022 yillarda elektrotexnika sanoatida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini yaratish va ishlab chiqarishni diversifikatsiya qilish dasturi doirasida amalga oshiriladigan investitsiya loyihalarini ishga tushirish bo'yicha tahlillar amalga oshirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *sanoat, transformatsiya, iqtisodiyot, mexanizm, usul, rivojlanish, elektronika, elektr jihozlari, O'zbekiston.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРОЦЕССОВ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ МЕХАНИЗМОВ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭЛЕКТРОТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ И РАСШИРЕНИЕ ИХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА В В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы трансформационных процессов на промышленных предприятиях. Цель данного исследования оценка*

состояния электронной промышленности в Узбекистане и предоставление предложений по её развитию. Согласно исследованиям, на сегодняшний день электронная промышленность Узбекистана имеет наибольшую численность занятых в промышленной группе региона. Более того, чистый продукт и доход от бизнеса в этом секторе быстро растут. В частности, в научно-исследовательской работе проведен анализ создания новых производственных мощностей в электротехнической отрасли в 2021-2022 годах и запуска инвестиционных проектов, которые будут реализованы в рамках программы диверсификации производства.

Ключевые слова: *промышленность, трансформация, экономика, механизм, метод. разработка, электроника, электрооборудование, Узбекистан*

Introduction

Over the past decades, the world has been rapidly moving towards a radically new type of economy, where digital technologies are becoming the main tool for its development and increasing competitiveness.

Digital transformation is a global and global trend that affects both developed and developing countries of the world, and digital technologies are increasing the trends of importance in accelerating the development of the economic systems of most countries.

Electronic industry enterprises have promoted efficiency in production and business and made great contributions to the development of the industry in particular and the economy of the province in general. In the coming period, the problem is that it is necessary to have appropriate directions and solutions to improve the efficiency of electronic industry enterprises, ensure sustainable development in the future, towards a common goal of socio-economic development in Uzbekistan.

Further deepening of the reforms carried out on the development of the electrical engineering industry, attracting foreign direct investment and modern technologies to the industry, deep processing of local raw materials, import substitution, competitive and high value in export markets. expanding the production of modern electrical engineering and electrical household products with added value

Systematic measures are being implemented in the republic to develop and modernize the electrical engineering industry, create new types of modern electrical engineering and electrical household products production facilities, increase the investment and export potential of the industry, as well as provide comprehensive support to local manufacturers [9].

Currently, in many countries of the world, digitalization has become one of the main priorities of strategic development along with innovation policy. For example, the Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing the state program "Digital Uzbekistan", where the main goal is to improve the quality of life of the population through the use of digital technologies, to accelerate the pace of economic development, to create conditions that allow the economy of Uzbekistan to move to a fundamentally new trajectory of development, which should ensure the creation of a digital economy of the future.

Materials And Methods

According to the forecasts of the world's leading experts, almost more than a quarter of the world economy will be digital by 2025. All spheres and sectors of the economy will be subject to digitalization: the public sector, the sector of large industrial enterprises, the sector of small and medium-sized businesses, and the social sphere. In other words, interaction schemes in digitalization will work: "B2B" (business – business); "B2C" (business – consumer); "C2C" (consumer – consumer); G2B (government - business); G2C (government - consumer). Considering this aspect, each country in the developed strategic plans should strive to provide for the development of those sectors of the economy that play the greatest role in the digitalization of production and economic processes.

The following should be defined as the main directions of development of the electrical industry:

- production of energy-saving, cheap and high-quality electrical engineering and electrical household products that replace imports, taking into account the needs of the domestic market;
- introduction of advanced technologies into deep processing of existing raw materials, expansion and diversification of production of finished products with high added value;
- development of mutual cooperative relations between the electrical engineering industry and other sectors of the economy, thereby increasing the level of localization of the production of components and equipment used in the electrical engineering industry;
- introducing modern methods of quality management and international standards into the electrical engineering industry, creating a certification system for domestically produced products in accordance with international requirements;
- production of new types of promising products in the electrical engineering industry, introduction of scientific research and experimental design developments and innovative ideas [10].

Understanding the Role of the Electrotechnical Industry in Development: Two Crucial Questions;

To fully comprehend the function of manufacturing in development, two critical questions must be addressed. First, what explains the phenomenon that the quicker electrotechnical production develops relative to GDP, the faster GDP appears to grow? Second, what factors contribute to the expansion of the manufacturing sector in the first place? Or, what factors limit the expansion of industrial output?

On the first question, it is worth noting that because differences in growth rates are largely explained by differences in labor productivity growth rather than differences in labor force growth rates, there must be some relationship between manufacturing sector growth and overall productivity growth. This is justified by two factors. The first is that whenever industrial production and output increase, labor resources are taken from sectors with open or disguised unemployment, such that labor transfers into manufacturing do not reduce output in these sectors and productivity growth outside of manufacturing grows. The existence of rising returns inside industry, both static and dynamic, is a second explanation. Static returns are a feature of manufacturing that come

from the size and scale of production units. When the factors of production are doubled, for example, output grows by a factor of more than two. Dynamic economies of scale are brought about through induced technological advancement and learning by doing, both of which are the outcome of production growth.

On the second topic, manufacturing production is not bound by supply-side resources; rather, a budding industrial sector need a market to sell to. Manufacturing expansion relies on agricultural demand in the early phases of development. Agriculture is the largest 'external' (independent) sector at this stage, emphasizing the importance of increased agricultural production in providing buying power and a growing market for industrial goods. However, the role of agriculture as an autonomous market for industrial goods declines with time, and exports eventually take over. In this regard, the ability of exporters to fund imports is a limitation.

Results and discussion

A digitalization of the economy for developing countries is a relatively new and promising direction. In the science of these countries, research has been conducted only to a small extent on the conceptual apparatus of digitalization of economic processes, the impact of digitalization processes on economic growth, the level of innovation and competitiveness of the economy, and social processes. The existing potential for predicting the prospects of digital development has also been studied to a small extent. The process of building a digital economy, relative to global digitalization processes – is a new stage in the development of developing countries based on the principles of “Industry 4.0” trends. It is important to build the main organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of digitalization at the macro and micro levels.

According to generally accepted encyclopedic data, the digital economy is the process of functioning of an economic system based on the complex application of computer technology, software, digital communications, and network communications [1].

The digital economy covers all subsystems of government activity, including:

- production of goods and services;
- distribution of goods and services;
- consumption of goods and services;
- cash flow (digital currency);
- social processes in society.

There is a different range of scientific approaches to understanding the essence of the digital economy. Thus, the digital economy is considered in the following interpretations:

- information economy;
- knowledge economy;
- innovative economy;
- e-economy;
- cybernetic economy.

Organizational and economic mechanisms for designing the development of the digital economy can be created and designed at the state (macroeconomic) level, as well as at the meso- and microeconomic levels.

Although the processes of digitalization at all economic levels can be carried out simultaneously, in modern theory, the first stage of digitalization should relate to the macroeconomic level.

The following measures to support the enterprises of the electrical engineering industry by the Export Promotion Agency should be introduced:

Until January 1, 2024, 50% of the cost of road, rail and air transport for the export of electrical engineering and electrical household products to all countries, including neighboring countries, but 15% of the export value of products (without transport costs) in road transport, railway providing subsidies for road transport in the amount of no more than 20%;

collateral for obtaining guarantees from local commercial banks regarding making (returning) advance payments within the framework of competitions (tenders), fulfilling contract terms in foreign currency, and ensuring warranty periods for delivered goods (works, services) regardless of funding sources providing guarantees up to 50% of the guarantee amount, but not exceeding 3 million US dollars.

The Government Commission on Export and Investment Development (S.U. Umurzakov) should approve the procedure for implementation of the support measures provided for in this paragraph within one month.

Profit tax and property tax for electrotechnical enterprises whose income from the sale of electrical engineering products is not less than 80 percent of their total income at the end of the reporting period from April 1, 2021 to January 1, 2024 to give tax benefits in the form of a 50% reduction in rates.

Funds allocated to the Fund from the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan are used for the following purposes:

covering 50% of the expenses related to the implementation of international standards in local enterprises producing electrical engineering and electrical household products, the certification of products in accordance with the requirements of foreign markets, but the equivalent of no more than 20,000 US dollars in one case;

covering the costs of the branch enterprises exporting high-added value copper products related to the production of products and their sale to foreign markets up to 6% of the export value, based on the types of products;

financing start-up projects, participating in the formation of chartered funds (capital) of production and service enterprises in the electrical engineering industry, establishing special engineering centers and experimental design bureaus;

in order to attract potential investors for the implementation of investment projects in the production of electrical engineering and electrical household products, repair and reconstruction of vacant and unused buildings and structures and improvement of external engineering and communication systems in them, as well as in areas specialized in the electrical engineering industry establishment of industrial technology parks;

providing short-term financial guarantees to local enterprises producing electrical engineering and electrical household products for participation in tenders;

reimbursement of 50% of the expenses of the enterprises of the electrotechnical industry network related to their participation in international exhibitions and fairs, but in one case the equivalent amount is not more than 10 thousand US dollars;

to conduct marketing of electrical engineering industry network enterprises to increase the popularity of products in foreign markets, to develop pre-project documents (business plan, technical and economic bases, etc.) of network projects, as well as to study the world market and carry out marketing analysis covering up to 50 percent of the costs associated with connecting to international databases (information resources);

organization of exhibitions and fairs in the republic and foreign countries, holding seminars, preparation of presentation materials and exhibition stands for the promotion of local electrical engineering and electrical household products.

Investment in capital construction of electronic industry enterprises is one of the most important investments in the construction and development of the digital economy. These investments will ensure sustainability in the medium and strategic term of the following sectors:

- state management of the economy;
 - functioning of the banking sector;
 - higher education sector;
 - healthcare industry;
 - electric power industry;
- the military-industrial complex [3].

Creation of new production capacities and diversification of production in the electrical engineering industry in 2021-2022

№	The area where the project is located	Project name	Project initiator	Annual capacity	Project cost (thousand dollars.)	from which:			Jobs (unit)	Start-up period
						funds of the initiator	bank loans	foreign direct investments		
136	Total:			-	531 921	169 542	228 220	137 659	9 657	-
43.	I. Household appliances and other consumer products			-	177 959	51 618	86 861	39 480	4 510	-

In 2021-2022, the creation of new production capacities in the electrical engineering industry and the launch of investment projects that will be implemented as part of the production diversification program

№	Name of the area	Number of projects (unit)	including that starts up:		Cost of projects (thousand dollars.)	including for those who will be employed:		Jobs (unit)	including for those who will be employed:	
			in 2021	in 2022		in 2021	in 2022		in 2021	in 2022
	Total:	136	45	91	531 921	138 095	393 826	9 657	3 010	6 647

Financing of investment projects to be implemented within the framework of the program of creation of new production capacities and diversification of production in the electrical engineering industry in 2021-2022

№	Name of the area	On projects that will be launched in 2021				On projects that will be launched in 2022			
		Cost of projects (thousand dollars.)	from which:			Cost of projects (thousand dollars.)	from which:		
			funds of the initiator	bank loans	directly foreign investments		funds of the initiator	bank loans	directly foreign investments
	Total:	138 095	53 550	70 645	13 900	393 826	115 992	157 575	123 759

Conclusion

Studying the organizational and economic mechanisms of designing the development of the digital economy, we can conclude that the processes of digitalization requires attention, both from the private sector of the economy and from the state. At the same time, the formation of the ecosystem of the digital economy is inherent in the state, which is endowed with tools for implementing policies at the macroeconomic level. Without the participation of microeconomics entities – enterprises, firms, companies, building a digital economy is also impossible since their digitalization processes are part of the ecosystem. At the same time, the digital economy should have a synergy of private and public capital.

Concentrate on infrastructure development: establish a clean land fund and the best conditions for infrastructure investors. Accelerate investment in technological infrastructure in industrial zones and clusters, as well as the formation of electronics industry clusters; Implement policies to promote and support businesses in developing industrial zones and clusters specializing in electronics and related sectors.

Improving environmental protection: The use, renovation, and protection of the environment are inextricably linked to the purpose of industrial growth. Failure to authorize or award construction licenses for investment projects, as well as carrying out construction without conducting an environmental impact assessment; Environmental protection propagation, education, and awareness raising Housing for employees, hospitals, and schools are examples of policies that prioritize, encourage, and enhance the social security system.

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Citation:

Nazarova, L.T. (2022). Organizational and economic issues of management at chemical industry enterprises. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (9), 66-74.

Nazarova, L.T. (2022). Kimyo sanoati korxonalarida boshqaruvning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy masalalari. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (9), 66-74.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7187550>

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ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC ISSUES OF MANAGEMENT AT CHEMICAL INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

Abstract. *The solution of the task of developing organizational and economic mechanisms of effective management in increasing the competitiveness of the chemical industry plays an important role, especially in the context of strengthening the processes of integration of the economy of our country into the world economy. The problems of harmonization and effective cooperation of Strategic and tactical priorities for the development of enterprises of the chemical industry are becoming today an urgent, but not methodically solved scientific and practical task. This article examines the issues of organizational and economic management at the enterprises of the chemical industry of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *chemical industry, development, innovation, management, industry, improvement of management system.*

KIMYO SANOATI KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUVNING TASHKILIY- IQTISODIY MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya. *Kimyo sanoatining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda samarali boshqaruvning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini ishlab chiqish vazifasini hal etish, ayniqsa, mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotining jahon iqtisodiyotiga integratsiyalashuvi jarayonlarini kuchaytirish sharoitida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kimyo sanoati korxonalarini rivojlantirishning strategik va taktik ustuvor yo'nalishlarini uyg'unlashtirish va samarali hamkorlik qilish muammolari bugungi kunda dolzarb, ammo metodik jihatdan hal etilmagan ilmiy va amaliy vazifaga aylanmoqda. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston kimyo sanoati korxonalarida tashkiliy-iqtisodiy boshqaruv masalalari o'rganilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kimyo sanoati, rivojlanish, innovatsiya, boshqaruv, sanoat, boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ХИМИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ

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Аннотация. *Решение задачи разработки организационно-экономических механизмов эффективного управления повышением конкурентоспособности химической промышленности приобретает особую значимость в условиях усиления процессов интеграции экономики нашей страны в мировую экономику. Проблемы гармонизации стратегических и тактических приоритетов развития предприятий химической промышленности и эффективного сотрудничества становятся сегодня актуальной, но методически нерешенной научно-практической задачей. В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы организационно-экономического управления на предприятиях химической промышленности Узбекистана.*

Ключевые слова: *химическая промышленность, развитие, инновации, управление, промышленность, совершенствование системы управления.*

Kirish

O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotining hozirgi holati sanoat sektorida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirishni, biznes amaliyotida sanoat biznesining sifat jihatidan o'sishini va uning ichki va tashqi bozorda raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlaydigan yangi boshqaruv vositalarini qo'llashni talab qiladi. Mikro darajadagi sanoat iqtisodiy tizimlarini rivojlantirishning strategik manfaatlari biznesni kapitallashtirishning o'sishiga, uning rivojlanishining barqarorligiga va dinamik o'zgaruvchan muhitda uzoq muddatli raqobatbardoshlikka va sanoat bozorlarining imkoniyatlariga erishishga qaratilgan. Boshqa tomondan, an'anaviy ravishda sanoat biznesini rivojlantirishni tezkor boshqarishning maqsadi joriy foyda va iqtisodiy samaradorlikni maksimal darajaga

ko'tarish hisoblanadi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, bozor, sanoat biznesi va sanoat bozorlarining institutsional o'zgarishi sharoitida iqtisodiy samaradorlik sanoat korxonalarini barqaror rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari bilan mutanosib ravishda tezkor boshqarish funksiyasi sifatida ko'rib chiqish zarurati yanada dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda.

Kimyo sanoati markazlashgan boshqaruv doirasida yaratilgan va boshqarilib, yagona iqtisodiy majmua sifatida qurilgan. Amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlar jarayonida bir xil sanoat maydonida joylashgan va bitta korxonaga vakili bo'lgan kimyo sanoati korxonalari bir-biridan mustaqil ravishda xususiyashtirildi va alohida aksiyadorlik jamiyatlariga ajratildi. Bu oxir-oqibat tovar zanjirlarining uzilishiga olib keldi. Sanoatning o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, hatto yirik kimyoviy zavodlarda ham texnologik jihatdan mahsulotlarni yetkazib berish zanjiridagi oraliq aloqalari bo'lib, ularning uzilishi eksportga individual aloqalarni yo'naltirishga, korxonalar yukining keskin pasayishiga olib keldi. Prezidentimiz tomonidan qabul qilingan "Kimyo sanoati korxonalarini yanada isloh qilish va moliyaviy sog'lomlashtirish, yuqori qo'shilgan qiymatli kimyoviy mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"¹gi qarori mamlakat kimyo sanoatining holatini, o'z hududida yirik kimyoviy majmualarga ega hududlarni, shuningdek sohadagi yetakchi korxonalarni jiddiy tahlil qilish va kimyo sanoatining barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlantirish yo'liga o'tishiga yordam beradigan tashkiliy va iqtisodiy mexanizmlarni shakllantirish yo'llarini izlash uchun asos yaratdi. Sanoat ishlab chiqarishining o'sishi, korxonalarining faol rivojlanishi, ularni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy transformatsiya sharoitida moslashtirish muammolari mahalliy va xorijiy olimlarning asarlarida aks ettirilgan.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini boshqarish nazariyasi va konsepsiyasi (klassik, natija, jarayon), kimyo sanoat biznesini bozor islohotining nazariy va amaliy muammolari bo'yicha fundamental tadqiqotlar natijalari, sanoat biznesini korporativ boshqarish uchun kontseptual asos hisoblanadi.

Tadqiqotning instrumental va uslubiy apparati sifatida qiyosiy, tizimli tahlil usullaridan foydalanildi. Tadqiqotning axborot va empirik bazasi O'zbekiston Respublikasi davlat statistika qo'mitasining rasmiy statistik materiallari, ko'rib chiqilgan qator masalalar bo'yicha sanoat korxonalarining faoliyati to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar hisoblanadi.

Tahlil va natijalar

O'zbekiston Respublikasining innovatsion rivojlanishi ko'p jihatdan ustuvor tarmoqlar, xususan, kimyo, biokimyoviy, gaz va neft-kimyo sanoatining (bundan buyon matnda kimyo sanoati deb yuritiladi) rivojlanishi bilan bevosita bog'liqdir. So'nggi yillarda sohada yaratilgan poydevor keyingi 3-5 yil davomida kimyo sanoati salohiyatining barqaror o'sish dinamikasini ta'minlashga qodir. Shu bilan birga, kimyo sanoatining barcha sohalarini uzoq muddatli progressiv rivojlantirish uchun mustahkam

¹ "Kimyo sanoati korxonalarini yanada isloh qilish va moliyaviy sog'lomlashtirish, yuqori qo'shilgan qiymatli kimyoviy mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" PQ-4992-sonli O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Qarori 13.02.2021.

bazani yaratish eng ilg'or xorijiy tajribani hisobga olgan holda sanoatni o'zgartirishni tezlashtirishni talab qiladi.

O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotini isloh qilishning yangi sharoitida kimyo sanoati rivojlanishini strategik qayta isloh qilish maqsadida, kimyo sanoatini o'zgartirishning asosiy uzoq muddatli strategik yo'nalishlari aniqlandi:

- texnologik transformatsiya-mahalliy xom ashyodan, shu jumladan organik sintez va nanotexnologiyalar orqali yarim tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish uchun yangi quvvatlar asosida xom ashyodan tayyor mahsulotga ko'p bog'lanishli qiymat zanjirlarini yaratish. Shu bilan birga, qayta ishlanmagan xom ashyo (tabiiy gaz, sanoat tuzi, paxta sellyulozasi, sirka kislotasi va boshqalar) eksportini bosqichma-bosqich kamaytirish mamlakatda ularni chuqur qayta ishlashni tashkil etish orqali;

- iqtisodiy munosabatlar tizimini o'zgartirish-birinchi navbatda qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqaruvchilari va kimyo sanoati korxonalarini o'rtasidagi munosabatlar sohasidagi davlat aralashuvini cheklash va eskirgan rejalashtirish va tarqatish tizimidan butunlay voz kechish;

- mulkiy munosabatlar tizimini o'zgartirish-sanoatda yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini yaratish va kimyo sanoati korxonalarini xususiylashtirishga xususiy kapitalni, shu jumladan xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish orqali kimyo sanoati korxonalarida davlat ulushini tubdan kamaytirish, shuningdek korxonalar faoliyatida davlat hokimiyati organlarining aralashuviga yo'l qo'ymaslik ;

- raqamli transformatsiya-moliyaviy, moddiy va kadrlar harakatini boshqarish, mahsulotlarni markalash, xalqaro moliyaviy hisobot standartlari asosida buxgalteriya tizimlarini joriy etish sohasiga zamonaviy dasturiy ta'minot tizimlarini joriy etish;

- fan va ishlab chiqarish o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqalarni o'zgartirish-innovatsion jarayonlarni tashkil etish va ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar asosida zamonaviy texnologiyalarni o'tkazishda fan va ishlab chiqarish o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqalarning yangi tizimini tashkil etish;

- kadrlar tayyorlash tizimini o'zgartirish-sohada kadrlar tayyorlash, qayta tayyorlash va malakasini oshirish tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish, shuningdek yuqori malakali mahalliy va xorijiy mutaxassislar tomonidan yaratilayotgan mavjud va yangi ishlab chiqarish obyektlarini kadrlar bilan ta'minlash.

Hozirgi bosqichda kimyo sanoatining holati, shuningdek, mamlakatning butun iqtisodiyoti ichki bozorda ham, tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatda ham muammolar bilan ajralib turadi. Korxonalar tashqi imkoniyatlarga ham, xavf-xatarlarga ham moslashishi, tegishli xatti-harakatlarni aniqlashi hamda strategiya va taktikaning atrof-muhitga samarali moslashishini ta'minlashi kerak.

1-jadval

Kimyo sanoati korxonalarida ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotlar hajmi

№	Yillar	Ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulot (mlrd,so'm)
1	2011	2594,7
2	2012	2924,7

3	2013	3350,1
4	2014	4130,1
5	2015	4993,7
6	2016	7378,9
7	2017	9893,8
8	2018	15078,4
9	2019	18974,3
10	2020	21213,5
11	2021	27577,9

O'zbekistonda kimyo mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish hajmi 2021 yilda 2020 yilga nisbatan 30 %ga ortgan bo'lib, bunga asosiy sabab sifatida korxonalarda amalga oshirilgan rekonstruktsiya ishlaridan keyingi samarali faoliyati hisoblanadi. So'nggi o'n yillikda respublikada kimyo mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish hajmi 9 barobarga ortdi.

Respublika bo'yicha kimyo mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish sur'atiga katta hissa qo'shib kelayotgan hududlardan biri bu Farg'ona viloyatidir. Farg'ona viloyatida kimyo mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish hajmi 2021 yilda 2020 yilga nisbatan 31 % ya'ni respublika o'sish ko'rsatkichlariga yaqin tendensiya aniqlandi.

Rivojlanish deganda korxonani doimiy, maqsadga muvofiq takomillashtirish, uning tarkibiy va funksional tarkibini yangilash, o'zgaruvchan muhitda ishlashning umumiy samaradorligini ta'minlash, yetarli daromad va tegishli xarajatlar tufayli xodimlar, boshqa korxonalar va tashkilotlar, davlat oldidagi barcha majburiyatlarni bajarish tushuniladi.

"Rivojlanish - qisqartirish" koordinatalarida korxonalarni rivojlantirishning turli holatlari, shu jumladan faol rivojlanish, barqaror rivojlanish, qayta qurish holati va bankrotlik holati ko'rib chiqiladi.

Korxonaning faoliyati va rivojlanishiga bevosita to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'sir ko'rsatadigan omillardan resurs yetkazib beruvchilar, iste'molchilar va raqobatchilar ta'kidlangan. Bilvosita ta'sir omillari orasida, birinchi navbatda, ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot yo'nalishlarining, shu jumladan jahon kimyo sanoatida, texnologik tuzilmalarning rivojlanishi va o'zgarishi, shuningdek davlatning sanoat va iqtisodiy siyosatining ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi.

Ushbu tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, korxonalar ishlashi kerak bo'lgan tashqi muhit, kimyo sanoati murakkab dinamik muhit bo'lib, sezilarli o'zgaruvchanlikka ega bo'lgan eng muhim omillarning ko'pligi va xilma-xilligi bilan ajralib turadi va adaptiv boshqaruvni yaratish zarurligini asoslaydi, uning vazifasi tizimning moslashuvchanligini saqlab qolishdir.

Shu bilan birga, moslashuv muammolarini hal qilishni ikki darajaga ajratish mumkin: mikroiqtisodiy-aniq iqtisodiy subyektlarning yangi iqtisodiy sharoitlarga bevosita moslashishi va makroiqtisodiy - rivojlanish va texnik xizmat ko'rsatish, shu jumladan davlat organlari tomonidan bozorda ishtirok etilishidir.

Kimyo sanoati yuqori moddiy va energiya intensivligi bilan ajralib turadi. Moddiy xarajatlar kimyoviy mahsulotlar narxining 70% dan ortig'ini tashkil qiladi va boshqa tarmoqlar orasida issiqlik energiyasi iste'moli bo'yicha birinchi va elektr energiyasi

iste'moli bo'yicha uchinchi o'rinda turadi. Yoqilg'i va energiya narxi ishlab chiqarish tannarxida 11% dan 25% gacha bo'lgan ulushlarga to'g'ri keladi.

Yuqoridagi jadvalda keltirilgan kimyo sanoatining tashkiliy-texnik xususiyatlari korxonaning barqaror rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan integratsiya, hamkorlik va ishlab chiqarish jarayonini tashkil etish shakllarini belgilaydigan sanoatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini to'liq aks ettiradi.

So'nggi yillarda sanoatning barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanish imkoniyatini cheklaydigan asosiy omillar mavjud, bu birinchi navbatda:

- iqtisodiy islohotlarning eng muhim vazifasini, ya'ni ishlab chiqarishni modernizatsiya qilishdan manfaatdor bo'lgan samarali egasini shakllantirishni ta'minlamagan xususiylashtirishning samarasiz sxemalari va mexanizmlari. Xususan, xususiylashtirishning eng ommaviy bosqichida kimyo majmuasida yangi mulkdorlarning moliyaviy majburiyatlari 25% dan kam bajarildi.

- raqobatbardosh mahsulot ishlab chiqarish uchun zarur shart-sharoitlarni ta'minlamaydigan past texnik daraja bilan ajralib turadigan sanoat ishlab chiqarish salohiyatining holati. Ishlab chiqarilgan kimyoviy mahsulotlarning yarmidan ko'pining sifat ko'rsatkichlari jahon standartlari talablariga javob bermaydi, bu yaqin kelajakda kimyo sanoat korxonalari uchun nafaqat tashqi, balki ichki bozorida ham vaziyatni jiddiy ravishda murakkablashtiradi.

- tabiiy monopoliyalar mahsulotlari (tabiiy gaz, neftni qayta ishlash zavodi mahsulotlari, elektr energiyasi, temir yo'l) uchun narxlar va tariflarning o'sish sur'atlari oshib bormoqda. Uch yil davomida kimyoviy mahsulotlar narxlarining oshishi bilan sanoat iste'molchilari uchun elektr energiyasi narxlarining oshishi.

Energiya resurslari narxlarining o'zgarishiga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri mutanosib ravishda kimyo majmuasi korxonalari foydalanadigan eng muhim xom ashyo va materiallar narxlarining o'sishi tezlashdi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, zamonaviy sharoitda O'zbekistonda kimyo sanoatini barqaror rivojlantirish muammosini hal qilish davlatning barcha darajalarida, shu jumladan davlat, sanoat, mintaqaviy darajada va alohida korxonada sanoatni tartibga solishning tashkiliy va iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirishni talab qiladi. Bu yerda asosiy rol davlatga tegishli bo'lishi kerak, uning maqsadi mamlakat kimyo majmuasini rivojlantirishni tezlashtirish bo'lishi lozim.

Shuningdek, kimyo sanoat korxonalarini boshqarishda to'rtta strategik yo'nalishlarga e'tibor qaratishi zarur:

- innovatsion mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishga, ilmiy tadqiqotlarni o'tkazishga, qiymat yaratish zanjirini raqamlashtirishga erishish;
- resurslardan oqilona foydalanish va xarajatlarni optimallashtirish orqali biznesni boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish;
- qiymat yaratish zanjiri bo'ylab qat'iy, ilmiy asoslangan tizimni rivojlantirish;
- korxonada samarali o'sishga yo'naltirilgan strategiyaga asoslangan holda resurslarni taqsimlash orqali qiymat yaratish, innovatsiyalarga asoslangan yuqori daromadli biznesda faoliyat ko'rsatish hisoblanadi.

Taklif etilayotgan yo'nalishlarning sohada kelgusida to'laqonli amalga oshirilishi kimyo sanoati korxonalarini faoliyatida qisqa vaqt ichida bozor munosabatlarini chuqurlashtirish, ularni rivojlantirish va boshqarishda mavjud omillarni samarali boshqarish va muvofiqlashtirish, yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan xatarlar darajasini pasaytirish imkonini beradi.

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Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

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Tarqatish hududi: O'zbekiston Respublikasi hamda belgilangan tartibda chet davlatlarga

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ISBN: 978-9943-7707-9-9

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880920>

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Бўлажак муҳандисларнинг лойиҳалаш компетенцияларини компьютер графикаси воситасида ривожлантириш методикаси: Монография / Мадаминов Ж.З. - Фарғона политехника институти. Фарғона, AL-FERGANUS, 2022. – 150 б.

ISBN: 978-9943-8579-0-2

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ISBN 978-9943-7707-5-1

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618980>

Э.Т.Мамуров, А.М.Гафуров

**CAD/CAM/CAE ТИЗИМЛАРИДА
ЛОЙИХАЛАШ АСОСЛАРИ**

Дарслик

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2022

**Мамуров Э.Т., Гафуров
А.М.** CAD/CAM/CAE
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ISBN 978-9943-7706-9-0

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йўналишлари бўйича
ўқув-услубий
бирлашмалар
фаолиятини
Мувофиқлаштирувчи
кенгаш томонидан
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тавсия этилган. (2022
йил 9 сентябр №302-
сонли буйруқ).*

E.T.Mamurov, Yu.Yu.Xusanov,
S.M.Yusupov

Mexatronika asoslari

Darslik

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E.T.Mamurov, S.M.Yusupov,
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YO'NALISHGA KIRISH

Darslik

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**MANAGEMENT OF
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Тўқимачилик саноати кластерлари
фаолиятида бошқарув механизмларини
такомиллаштириш

Монография

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ISBN: 978-9943-7707-7-5

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ISBN 978-9943-7707-6-8

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6750455>

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